

THE ROLE OF REGIONAL TAX AUTONOMY, FIRM SIZE, AND BUSINESS GROUPS IN TAX AVOIDANCE: EVIDENCE FROM SPAIN [☆]

Aitor Garmendia-Lazcano¹, Laura Baselga-Pascual²

Abstract

This paper investigates the influence of regional tax autonomy, firm size, and business group affiliation on corporate tax burden in a large sample of Spanish firms, including non-listed firms, from 2007 to 2016. Our findings reveal that firms located in tax-autonomous regions exhibit lower effective corporate tax rates (ETR), providing new empirical support for the horizontal tax competition theory. Additionally, we identify a positive relationship between firm size and corporate tax burden, aligning with the political cost theory. Furthermore, we find that group-affiliated firms face a higher ETR than independent firms, and that group affiliation attenuates the differences in the tax burden experienced by large and small firms.

JEL classification: G30, H25, H26 M21, O52

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¹ University of Deusto. Deusto Business School, Department of Finance and Economics. Address: Mundaiz Kalea, 50, 20012 Donostia, Gipuzkoa, Spain. E-mail: aitor.garmendia@deusto.es.

² University of Deusto. Deusto Business School, Department of Finance and Economics. Address: Mundaiz Kalea, 50, 20012 Donostia, Gipuzkoa, Spain. E-mail: lbaselga@deusto.es.

1. Introduction

Corporate tax avoidance has emerged as a pivotal issue for regulators and policymakers worldwide. International organizations, such as the IMF, OECD, and the European Commission¹, have enacted measures to curb tax avoidance and alleviate disparities in corporate tax rates across nations. This has sparked a debate on whether fiscal autonomy among countries triggers a "race to the bottom". Similarly, tax competition can also manifest within a country among different regions. In Spain, regional tax competition is a prevalent topic in public discourse² and a significant concern for politicians and regulators.

In this setting, our research aims to investigate whether firms situated in Spain's tax-autonomous regions, referred to as "foral territories", experience a lower corporate tax burden compared to those in non-autonomous regions, known as "common territory". Spain represents an interesting case study due to the full tax authority granted to foral territories, which allows them to operate under a distinctive fiscal framework in contrast to the common territory. This unique setup provides a prime opportunity to empirically test the theory of horizontal tax competition, which argues that mobile productive factors tend to gravitate towards jurisdictions with lower tax rates, thereby motivating regulators to lessen tax burdens to attract these factors (Zodrow and Mieszkowski, 1986; Wilson, 1986).

Previous research in Spain suggests a lower effective tax burden in foral territories compared to the common territory (e.g., Romero et al., 2009; Molina, 2012; Martínez et al., 2015) or portrays a similar tax avoidance across both (Granados et al., 2021). However, these studies are primarily descriptive. Thus, their conclusions must be approached with caution, as the differences observed might not solely stem from the geographical location of the firms but from other intrinsic characteristics of each region's companies, such as size, profitability, leverage, etc. which significantly impact the effective tax burden but are not addressed by these studies. A multivariate analysis, such as ours, offers a more robust assessment of the tax avoidance differences between the foral and common territories by controlling for specific characteristics of the firm and the territory that significantly affect the effective tax burden.

The second objective of this research is to provide additional empirical evidence on the theories of political cost and political power in Spanish firms. Political cost theory posits that larger firms endure lower tax avoidance due to their high public visibility, which subjects them to intensified governmental regulatory actions and elevated social responsibility expectations (Jensen and Meckling, 1976; Watts and Zimmerman, 1986; Zimmerman, 1983). Conversely, the political power theory contends that large firms can leverage their influence to secure tax benefits that diminish their tax liabilities (Siegfried, 1972). Previous international studies examining these theories have produced mixed or inconclusive results (Zimmerman, 1983; Porcano, 1986; Gupta y Newberry, 1997; Harris and Feeny, 2003; Rego, 2003; Plesko, 2003; Adhikari et al., 2006; Richardson and Lanis, 2007; Chen et al., 2010; Delgado et al. 2014; Molina and Barberá, 2017, among others). In the Spanish context, empirical evidence supports

the political cost theory (Calvé et al., 2005; Granados et al., 2021, 2022; Bona-Sánchez et al., 2023), while other studies endorse the political power theory (Fernández-Rodríguez et al., 2019; Bona-Sánchez et al., 2019; Castillo-Murciego and López-Laborda, 2022). Further research shows a nonlinear relationship between ETR and firm size (Martínez et al., 2015; Moreno-Rojas et al., 2017), and some find no clear link between firm size and tax avoidance (Fernández-Rodríguez, 2004; Monterrey et al., 2010; Molina, 2012; Barbera et al., 2020). Many of these studies have concentrated on partial samples, such as publicly listed companies, specific sectors, or certain legal forms, potentially skewing their outcomes. Our study aims to transcend these limitations by employing a comprehensive multisectoral sample of 16,400 firms across Spain, including over 90% small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), as well as listed and unlisted companies. This broader approach offers a more comprehensive view of the Spanish corporate landscape to evaluate these political cost and power theories.

Our third objective seeks to determine if the potential for incurring higher reputational costs encourages group-affiliated firms to avoid aggressive tax practices (Graham et al., 2014). To do so, we explore the correlation between business group affiliation and tax avoidance, and the impact of group affiliation on the relationship between firm size and tax avoidance. By examining this potential moderating effect, we propose that firms within business groups might display traits akin to those of large firms. This analysis of the moderating effect addresses a gap in the previous literature, providing new insights into the dynamics that underpin the theories of political power and political cost.

Through the application of a multivariate analysis on panel data, our findings indicate that firms in foral territories, which benefit from fiscal autonomy, incur a lower tax burden compared to those in common territory. This fact is corroborated by a model that includes, among other variables, a control for the statutory tax rates (STR) of each region, indicating that the higher tax avoidance observed in the foral territories is due to additional tax advantages (e.g., deductions) that go beyond statutory rates and allow firms to reduce their effective rates. Furthermore, our analysis confirms that both larger firms and those within business groups face lower tax avoidance, supporting the political cost theory. This finding aligns with prior research such as Watts and Zimmerman (1978), Richardson and Lanis (2007), Belz et al. (2019), and Stamatopoulos et al. (2019), among others. The increased visibility of these firms heightens their susceptibility to reputational risks associated with adopting aggressive tax practices, overshadowing any potential benefits. Additionally, our results indicate that affiliation to a business group moderates the relationship between firm size and tax avoidance, with smaller firms in groups experiencing a tax avoidance similar to that of larger firms, thereby reducing size-related disparities observed in non-affiliated firms. These findings are robust, enduring tests through alternative dependent variables and replication analysis using different samples.

This article contributes to the literature in several key ways. First, it significantly enriches the discourse on tax competition among territories by introducing new empirical evidence supporting the theory of

horizontal tax competition (Bucovetsky, 1991; Wilson, 1991; Vandebussche et al., 2005). By implementing a multivariate analysis that incorporates numerous tax avoidance determinants identified by the literature, our study expands upon the descriptive works of Romero et al. (2009) and Granados et al. (2021), providing a quantitative approach that isolates the effects of control variables, alleviates endogeneity issues, and yields more reliable conclusions. This study is pioneering in directly addressing this topic through a multivariate approach in Spain. Additionally, it highlights the importance of additional tax benefits (e.g., deductions), beyond statutory rates, in increasing tax avoidance in foral territories compared to common territory.

Second, this research provides new empirical validation of the political cost theory using a comprehensive, multisectoral sample of Spanish firms, predominantly SMEs, diverging from most previous Spanish studies which have focused on partial samples (listed companies, specific sectors, etc.). This approach offers a more representative snapshot of the Spanish corporate landscape. Moreover, it adds to the understanding of political power and cost theories by showing that group affiliation, similar to size, reduces tax avoidance. Thus, both larger firms and those affiliated with groups experience the dominance of political cost over political power.

Third, this study introduces a novel contribution to the literature on political power and cost theories by showing, for the first time, that group affiliation moderates the relationship between firm size and tax avoidance. We find that the negative effect of size on tax avoidance is mitigated in firms affiliated with groups, showing that small firms within business groups experience a comparable level of tax avoidance to that of larger firms. This finding suggests that, in terms of tax avoidance, a small firm integrated into a group might face challenges similar to those of large firms, such as increased governmental supervision and regulation or the demand for greater social responsibility, which entail higher political and reputational costs associated with adopting aggressive tax strategies (Morck and Nakamura, 1999; Kim et al., 2004; Dewenter et al., 2001; Morck et al., 2005).

The remainder of the article is structured as follows. Section 2 provides an overview of the general characteristics of corporate income tax in Spain. Section 3 reviews relevant literature and presents our research hypotheses. Section 4 describes the model formulation and the variables used in our analysis. Section 5 details the sample description. Section 6 presents the main results of our multivariate analysis. Section 7 examines the robustness of our findings through additional tests. Finally, Section 8 discusses the implications and conclusions, and Section 9 assesses the limitations and suggests future lines of research.

2. Corporate income tax in Spain

The corporate income tax applies to firms with residency in Spain, defined by the location of their registered or effective head office within the country. The responsibility for the design, administration, and collection of this tax lies with the central government, except in two autonomous communities, the

Basque Country and Navarre, which have tax autonomy. Regions following central government regulations are referred to as the "common territory", while the Basque Country and Navarre, with their own tax regulations, are known as the "foral territories". Within the foral territories, each province (Alava, Biscay, Gipuzkoa, and Navarre) has the autonomy to design and collect its own corporate income tax.

During the study covered period, from 2007 to 2016, the corporate general tax rate in the common territory decreased from 32.5% in 2007 to 25% in 2016³. However, specific cases are subject to different rates, such as newly created firms, small companies, cooperatives, foundations and associations, credit institutions, and hydrocarbon firms. Similarly, in all three provinces of the Basque Country, the nominal general rate remained at 28% from 2007 to 2016. In Navarre, the rate decreased from 32.5% to 28% during the same period. Like the common territory, these foral territories also consider special cases with different tax rates. Appendix A illustrates the evolution of the statutory corporate tax rate across different regions during this time span.

However, in addition to varying STRs, differences in ETRs across territories can arise due to the application of deductions and other tax benefits. Corporate tax regulations include deductions in both the common and foral territories, with notable distinctions between them. Foral laws often provide more generous deductions for similar expenses. For example, R&D deductions are 30% in the Basque Country and 40% in Navarre, compared to 25% in common territory. Additionally, foral laws include extra deductions unavailable in common territory, such as those for investments in new fixed assets, projects promoting sustainable development and energy efficiency or electric mobility.

Another significant aspect of the Spanish corporate tax law between 2007 and 2016 is the regime for joint taxation to the central and the foral administrations. Companies with revenues equal to or less than €7 million were taxed exclusively in the territory (foral or common) where their registered office was located, according to the fiscal regulations of that territory. On the other hand, companies with revenues exceeding €7 million that conducted 100% of their operations in a foral or common territory, were taxed exclusively in the territory in which they operated and according to the fiscal regulations of said territory, regardless of their registered office. Furthermore, companies with revenues exceeding €7 million operating in both foral and common territories were subject to joint taxation in both territories in proportion to the volume of operations (revenues) conducted in each territory. Within this group, if the company was headquartered in the Basque Country or Navarre and conducted less than 75% of its operations in the common territory, the joint taxation was regulated according to the corresponding foral regulations. Conversely, companies headquartered in the Basque Country or Navarre that conducted 75% or more of their operations in the common territory were subject to joint taxation regulated according to the central government's tax rules.

Given previous limitation, in our “Robustness checks” section, we replicate our baseline analysis using a subsample of firms with revenues equal to or less than 7 million euros to focus on firms that are exclusively taxed in the territory where their registered office is located.

An additional feature of the common territory is the existence of special tax regulations for the Canary Islands, Ceuta, and Melilla, granting them significant tax advantages due to geographical reasons. Furthermore, the Canary Islands benefit from reduced taxation linked to the Canary Islands Special Zone (ZEC)⁴. This special economic zone applies a low tax rate (currently set at 4%) to certain activities, aiming to promote economic development in the islands.

Considering the aforementioned characteristics, Spain presents itself as an intriguing case study to examine potential differences in the effective corporate tax rates among firms situated in the foral and common territories.

3. Related literature and research hypotheses

3.1 Tax avoidance and tax autonomy regions

Literature shows that tax autonomy leads to tax competition. Keen (2008) defines tax competition as a non-cooperative fiscal adjustment strategy between jurisdictions, wherein each government adjusts its tax system parameters based on the fiscal policy moves of other jurisdictions. The "tax competition" hypothesis is based on the notion that, under *ceteris paribus* conditions, production factors tend to be located in lower-taxed areas such as cities, regions, states, or countries (Zodrow and Mieszkowski, 1986; Wilson, 1986). Consequently, governments strive to reduce the tax burden to attract these production factors.

Tax competition can emerge both between countries and among sub-national jurisdictions within a country (Wilson, 1999). In this context, fiscal interactions can result in horizontal and vertical externalities (Brühlhart and Jametti, 2006; Fox et al., 2015). Vertical externality arises when different jurisdictional levels, such as national and regional, tax the same tax base. This interaction may lead to tax rates exceeding the social optimum, although empirical results remain inconclusive (Besley and Rosen, 1998; Goodspeed, 2000; Hayashi and Boadway, 2001; Keen and Kotsogiannis, 2002; Brühlhart and Jametti, 2006; Da Costa et al., 2015).

Horizontal externality occurs when governments from different territories, be it national or regional, compete for mobile production factors and tax bases by setting lower tax rates or offering other tax incentives. Several studies on corporate tax competition support the theory that this horizontal competition between neighbouring countries triggers a "race to the bottom" (Hansson and Olofsdotter, 2005; Overesch and Rincke, 2011). Tax havens serve as relevant examples, offering very low tax rates and additional advantages like privacy (Tobin and Walsh, 2013). Consequently, neighbouring countries often lower their tax rates in an attempt to attract investment.

Other studies analyse horizontal tax competition among regions within the same country. For instance, Vandebussche et al. (2005) found evidence of horizontal tax competition among regions in Belgium, where variations in effective tax rates (ETR) of large Belgian firms between 1993 and 2002 were attributed to the firms' operating region. The authors argued that peripheral regions decreased their tax burdens to attract business investments from core regions. They also suggested that, besides reducing STRs, governments may employ other mechanisms to lower firms' tax bases and attract specific investments, such as preferential tax treatment, tax credits, and tax deductions. Additionally, Bucovetsky (1991) and Wilson (1991) argued that smaller jurisdictions can impose lower taxes and are better positioned to compete for capital inflows compared to larger regions.

In Spain, corporate tax competition between the common territory and the foral territories closely resembles a horizontal competition model. Foral governments have exclusive authority to tax the base within their territories and can engage in a "race to the bottom" to attract production factors and mobile tax bases. Moreover, the foral territories are considerably smaller in size than the common territory and are located on the periphery of Spain. Consequently, their incentives to reduce the tax burden may be more pronounced (Bucovetsky, 1991; Wilson, 1991; Vandebussche et al., 2005). Previous research examining the differences in effective taxation across various Spanish regions has been limited. These studies indicate a lower effective tax burden in foral territories compared to common territories (e.g., Romero et al., 2009; Molina, 2012; Martínez et al., 2015) or suggest similar tax avoidance in both (Granados et al., 2021). However, these results must be interpreted with caution as they belong to descriptive studies lacking a multivariate analysis approach and may be subject to endogeneity. For instance, they do not consider the effect that other firm-specific variables (e.g., size, profitability, leverage, etc.) and regional variables (e.g., STR) might have on the corporate effective tax burden. Therefore, it is necessary to undertake a multivariate analysis to perform a more robust evaluation of the existing differences in tax avoidance between the foral territories and the common territory.

Following results from Bucovetsky (1991), Wilson (1991), and Vandebussche et al. (2005), given that foral territories can be considered peripheral and small regions in Spain, we anticipate that they offer more favorable fiscal conditions to attract capital and resources. Consequently, firms located in these territories might experience lower ETRs. Moreover, considering that foral laws not only generally provide larger deductions for similar types of expenses but also encompass a broader range of deductible concepts, as discussed in section 2, we expect that, even after adjusting for disparities in the statutory corporate tax rate, firms located in foral territories will still incur lower tax burdens. Thus, we propose the following hypothesis:

H1: Firms located in foral territories experience lower tax burdens than those located in the common territory.

3.2 Tax avoidance and firm size

The relationship between firm size and tax avoidance is supported by two opposing theories: the political power theory and the political cost theory. The political power theory posits that larger firms leverage their influence to secure favorable treatment and tax savings. These firms are more inclined to engage in tax planning and adopt accounting practices that reduce their effective taxes due to their access to substantial financial and legal resources. Numerous international empirical studies provide evidence supporting this theory, revealing a positive correlation between firm size and tax avoidance (Siegfried, 1972; Derashid and Zhang, 2003; Harris and Feeny, 2003; Janssen, 2005; Adhikari et al., 2006). In Spain, the research of Fernández-Rodríguez et al. (2019), Bona-Sánchez et al. (2019), and Castillo-Murciego and López-Laborda (2022) also support this theory, primarily studying the reality of publicly listed companies. They conclude that the presence of former politicians on corporate boards or the strategies of shifting profits to low-tax countries allow larger Spanish firms to reduce their tax burden.

Conversely, the political cost theory suggests a negative relationship between firm size and tax avoidance. According to this theory, larger organizations, being more visible, attract heightened government scrutiny, resulting in elevated tax burdens. These firms are expected to exhibit social responsibility by paying more taxes to uphold their corporate image and mitigate reputational costs. Several international empirical studies substantiate this theory (e.g.: Watts and Zimmerman, 1978; Zimmerman, 1983; Watts and Zimmerman, 1986; Belz et al., 2019; Stamatopoulos et al., 2019). In the Spanish context, the studies conducted by Calvé et al. (2005) with a sample of small-sized companies from the Valencian Community, Granados et al. (2021) with both listed and unlisted companies, Granados et al. (2022) with companies in the tourism sector, and Bona-Sánchez et al. (2023) with a sample of listed companies, confirm the political cost theory.

However, there are also studies indicating that the relationship between the ETR and firm size is not linear, as it is positive up to a certain size and then turns negative (Bao and Romeo, 2013; Delgado et al., 2018). In Spain, this conclusion is reached by the descriptive work of Martínez et al. (2015) on cooperative firms and by Moreno-Rojas et al. (2017) on companies in the tourism sector. Additionally, other studies conclude that there is no significant relationship between tax avoidance and size. In the Spanish context, examples include the work of Fernández-Rodríguez (2004) studying listed companies, Monterrey et al. (2010) analyzing differences between family and non-family firms, Molina (2012) with his descriptive study on cooperatives, and Barbera et al. (2020) examining listed companies.

This divergence in results underscores the need for further research on this topic. Additionally, in the Spanish context, it is observed that most works have studied only listed companies (Fernández-Rodríguez, 2004; Bona-Sánchez et al., 2019; Barbera et al., 2020; Castillo-Murciego and López-Laborda, 2022; Bona-Sánchez et al., 2023), specific sectors (Moreno-Rojas et al., 2017; Granados et al.,

2022) and regions (Calvé et al., 2005), or cooperative firms (Molina, 2012; Martínez et al., 2015). This limitation may have influenced their results.

Therefore, our research aims to overcome these limitations by examining the relationship between firm size and tax avoidance across a multisectoral sample, with a significant presence of SMEs including both listed and unlisted companies, and a variety of legal forms. We consider this approach provides a more comprehensive perspective of the Spanish corporate landscape. Moreover, although the low institutional trust rate in Spain (OECD, 2023) and the higher perception of corruption compared to other European nations (Transparency International, 2022) might be conducive to fostering the political power of large firms, Spain is also a developed country with a high Human Development Index of 0.9 (UNDP, 2022) suggesting independent and robust institutions. This supports the prevalence of the political cost theory, as it limits the influence of large corporations (Moreno-Rojas et al., 2017; Granados et al., 2022; Bona-Sánchez et al., 2023).

Considering this context and the predominance of small-sized enterprises in the Spanish business environment, we believe that the forces of political cost will dominate over the forces of political power. Therefore, we propose the following hypothesis:

H2: There is a negative relationship between the size of a firm and its corporate tax avoidance.

3.3 Tax avoidance, firm size, and business groups

Numerous authors have identified a positive correlation between affiliation with business groups and tax avoidance (Gramlich et al., 2004; Mills and Newberry, 2004; Beuselinck and Deloof, 2014). The literature emphasizes that belonging to a group provides companies access to both tangible and intangible resources within the group (Khanna and Palepu, 1999; Guillén, 2000; Granovetter, 2005). In fiscal terms, this means that integration into a group facilitates the exchange of experiences, skills, and resources to reduce tax burdens (Kang and Kim, 2021). For example, strategies such as the transfer of income between subsidiaries are commonly used to minimize the group's tax liabilities (Vandenbussche and Tan, 2005; Jung et al., 2009; Dyreng and Lindsey, 2009). Additionally, even smaller companies can benefit from the political power derived from their participation in a group, which may allow the groups to influence government policies, negotiate preferential tax treatments, or achieve privileged access to financial resources, thereby attaining greater tax avoidance (Morck and Yeung, 2004; Khanna and Yafeh, 2007). Therefore, from this perspective, the relationship between group affiliation and tax avoidance is governed by dynamics very similar to those observed in political power theory.

However, while business groups can offer multiple avenues for aggressive tax planning, they do not always achieve lower ETRs compared to independent firms. For instance, in a study on American multinational groups, Rego (2003) found a positive correlation between foreign income and ETRs, indicating that profit-shifting strategies might not be as effective in these groups. Similarly, Blouin and

Robinson (2020) suggest that some studies might have exaggerated the extent of profit shifting by multinationals due to double-counting of foreign profits, which could result in an underestimation of ETRs. Moreover, firms in business groups may show greater resilience during economic downturns due to the protective nature of the group, but they might also face higher tax obligations.

Furthermore, firms affiliated with groups may also face increased public and governmental scrutiny due to their economic and social significance, entailing high reputational risks and greater demands for social responsibility (Dewenter et al., 2001). In this vein, Christensen et al. (2022) suggest that, in multinational companies, the risks of fines and reputational damage may deter the adoption of aggressive tax practices. Likewise, Su and Tan (2018) demonstrate that business groups operating in tax havens experience diverse reputational consequences, and their findings also indicate that business groups with a pro-social orientation tend to establish fewer companies in tax havens. Therefore, as groups evolve, they may develop a pro-social identity that discourages ethically questionable practices such as tax avoidance. From this perspective, we again observe that the forces underlying political cost theory govern the relationship between group affiliation and tax avoidance.

Consequently, from the perspective of political power and political cost, business groups display many characteristics associated with large firms, such as extensive resource availability, significant political influence, high visibility, and heightened concern for the reputational consequences of aggressive tax practices. These attributes suggest a substantial overlap in the dynamics that influence both large firms and group-affiliated firms. Therefore, within the Spanish institutional context, we predict a similar predominance of political cost forces over political power in shaping the tax behavior and strategies of group-affiliated companies. Considering these factors, we propose our third hypothesis:

H3: There is a negative correlation between group affiliation and corporate tax avoidance.

Finally, although previous studies have not specifically addressed the moderating effect of group affiliation on the relationship between firm size and tax avoidance, we believe this effect may be significant. On one hand, from the perspective of political power, small firms affiliated with groups can benefit from the tax advantages garnered through the group's political influence and its expertise in optimizing tax planning strategies (Khanna and Palepu, 1999; Guillén, 2000; Faccio and Lang, 2002; Granovetter, 2005; Locorotondo et al., 2012). This may result in an equalization of tax avoidance between large and small group-affiliated firms, as all members of the group equally benefit from the group's political power advantages.

On the other hand, from the perspective of political cost, small firms integrated into groups may face disadvantages similar to those of larger firms. Being part of a group can subject them to greater scrutiny and regulatory attention from public authorities, as well as heightened demands for socially responsible behavior as part of a corporate group. Moreover, the business group may seek to mitigate reputational damage that could negatively impact the value and performance of the group's companies if one of its

members is involved in a potential tax scandal (Graham et al., 2014; Hanlon and Slemrod, 2019; Baudot et al., 2020). Consequently, for small firms affiliated with groups, this can increase the political and reputational costs associated with adopting aggressive tax practices, aligning them with those of larger firms (Morck and Nakamura, 1999; Kim et al., 2004; Dewenter et al., 2001; Morck et al., 2005). Thus, in group-affiliated firms, the tax avoidance on both large and small firms is equalized downwards, attenuating the differences in tax pressure they face.

Therefore, given that in group-affiliated firms, the dynamics of political power and political cost appear to mitigate the effect of size on tax avoidance, promoting similar tax behavior among both large and small firms, we propose our fourth hypothesis:

H4: The negative correlation between firm's size and its tax avoidance is attenuated within business groups.

4. Model formulation and variables

4.1 Model formulation

To test our hypotheses, we employ various dynamic panel data models to assess the robustness of our findings. This constitutes the specification of our baseline dynamic analytical model:

$$TA_{it} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 TA_{it-1} + \alpha_2 BCD_{it} + \alpha_3 NAD_{it} + \alpha_4 SIZE_{it} + \alpha_5 GD_{it} + \alpha_6 (SIZE_{it} \times GD_{it}) + \phi X_{it} + \eta_i + d_t + i_{it} + v_{it}$$

where TA_{it} denotes firm's tax avoidance; TA_{it-1} is the lagged dependent variable that captures the dynamic nature of tax avoidance; BCD_{it} and NAD_{it} are indicator variables, denoting whether a firm's registered office is located in the foral territories of the Basque Country and Navarre; $SIZE_{it}$ is the firm's size; GD_{it} is a dummy variable that indicates whether a firm is group-affiliated; $SIZE_{it} \times GD_{it}$ is the interaction term between firm size and group affiliation; and X_{it} is a set of time-variant control variables taken from the literature. η_i denotes firm-specific time-invariant unobservable characteristics; d_t measures the time-specific fixed effects and i_{it} represents the industry dummies for firm i in year t to control for potential industry fixed effects on tax avoidance. Finally, v_{it} represents the disturbance term.

This model allows us to examine the relationships between tax avoidance, regional tax autonomy, firm size, group affiliation, and other control variables while accounting for time-specific and firm-specific fixed effects as well as potential industry-specific effects.

4.2 Dependent variables

In line with Hanlon and Heitzman (2010), the term "tax avoidance" is defined as a reduction of explicit taxes⁵. This broad definition encompasses various transactions that have an impact on a firm's explicit tax liability, including both legal tax planning and illegal activities. To measure tax avoidance, four proxies are used. The first proxy is the ETR, which is defined as the total income tax expense divided by pre-tax book income. The ETR is a widely used measure of tax avoidance in the literature (Gupta

and Newberry, 1997; Richardson and Lanis, 2007; Chen et al., 2010; Lanis and Richardson, 2012; Landry et al., 2013). To ensure the reliability of the ETR, certain observations are removed from the analysis. Specifically, observations with zero or negative pre-tax book income or tax refunds are excluded, as they distort the ETR. Additionally, observations with ETRs exceeding 100% are dropped due to potential model estimation problems. As a result, the ETR variable ranges between 0 and 100%.

Tax avoidance activities often lead to reduced ETRs by creating book-tax differences between a firm's book and taxable incomes. Therefore, tax-motivated transactions typically result in lower ETRs (Rego, 2003; Chen et al., 2010). Furthermore, firms can utilize their foreign operations to lower their tax liabilities, and the ETR adequately captures this form of tax avoidance. Despite its merits, the ETR measure has limitations. Firstly, it does not reflect tax strategies that defer taxes. Secondly, it fails to distinguish between activities that benefit taxes and deliberate tax avoidance activities. Lastly, it focuses solely on nonconforming tax strategies, thus not capturing book-tax-conforming tax avoidance activities, i.e., transactions that reduce both book income and taxable income (Hanlon and Heitzman, 2010; Badertscher et al., 2019).

To overcome some of these limitations, we use three additional tax avoidance proxies. Following Dyreng et al. (2008), the second measure of tax avoidance used in this study is a long-term ETR (ETR3Y), which aims to reduce the volatility of the annual ETR. ETR3Y is calculated by summing the total income tax expense of the current year (t) and the two preceding years (t-1 and t-2) and dividing it by the cumulative pre-tax book income of those three years (Hsu and Liu, 2018; Sanchez-Marin et al., 2016). Similar to the ETR measure, we truncate ETR3Y between 0 and 100%.

Furthermore, to enhance the comparison of the tax burden among regions with distinct STRs and to discern signs of tax competition, we develop two additional ratios. ETR/STR is defined as the annual ETR divided by the prevailing STR in the region where the firm's registered office is located. ETR3Y/STR3Y is calculated as the ratio between ETR3Y and the three-year average STR (Schaffer and Turley, 2001). In both cases, a ratio close to 1 indicates that the effective rate is close to the statutory rate, reflecting the limited relevance of fiscal mechanisms such as exemptions or deductions in reducing the tax liability. Conversely, a ratio below 1 indicates that the ETR deviates from the statutory rate, highlighting the greater relevance of these tax avoidance mechanisms.

4.3 Main explanatory variables

Two dummy variables, BCD and NAD, are created to identify Spanish regions with tax autonomy for corporate income tax design and collection. BCD is set to 1 when the firm's registered office is in the Basque Country and 0 otherwise, while NAD is set to 1 when the firm's registered office is in Navarre and 0 otherwise.

Due to the unavailability of disaggregated data on firms' operations by territory, the study assumes that firms with revenues exceeding €7 million⁶ are taxed according to the tax rules of the territory where their registered office is located. It should be noted that this assumption is a limitation of the study.

Consistent with previous studies in the tax avoidance literature (Gupta and Newberry, 1997; Richardson and Lanis, 2007; Dyreng et al., 2008, among others), firm size (SIZE) is measured as the natural logarithm of total assets.

A business group is defined as a set of firms controlled by a parent company through ownership chains with links exceeding 50% ownership (Gramlich et al., 2004). To identify Spanish business groups from 2007 to 2016, an algorithm is designed using the SABI database. The algorithm utilizes annual data from 2007 to 2016, including the directory of active Spanish firms and direct shareholdings of any shareholder with more than 50% ownership obtained from the subsidiaries and shareholders data. The iterative algorithm begins by identifying the direct majority shareholder of each Spanish firm in the directory. If the identified shareholder is an individual or a family, the search terminates. However, if the shareholder is another firm, the algorithm continues by searching through its shareholders until it identifies a final firm that is not owned by any other firm. In this manner, the ownership chain linking each firm to its parent company is constructed. All Spanish firms ultimately owned by another firm or heading business groups are classified as group-affiliated firms, and the dummy variable GD takes the value 1.

4.4 Control variables

The study incorporates several firm-specific control variables based on previous research in the tax avoidance literature (e.g., Rego, 2003; Vandenbussche et al., 2005; Lanis and Richardson, 2012; Guenther et al., 2013; Landry et al., 2013; Sánchez-Marín et al., 2016; Stamatopoulos et al., 2019; Kovermann and Wendt, 2019). These control variables capture various factors that may influence a firm's corporate tax burden.

Ownership concentration (OC) is measured by the main shareholder's equity share, indicating the percentage of direct shareholding held by the main shareholder in the firm. It should be noted that this shareholding does not necessarily have to be a majority one. To calculate OC, all direct shareholdings from the SABI database's shareholders and subsidiaries data are integrated, and the highest shareholding for each firm is selected. The impact of ownership structure on tax avoidance has conflicting views in the literature. Some studies suggest that a higher concentration of ownership in family firms reduces tax avoidance (e.g: Chen et al., 2010; Sánchez-Marín et al., 2016), while others indicate that tax avoidance increases with the percentage of family ownership (Kovermann and Wendt, 2019).

Company profitability is captured by the return on assets (ROA). The literature presents mixed findings regarding the relationship between profitability and tax avoidance. While some studies indicate that

more profitable firms tend to have higher ETRs (e.g.: Gupta and Newberry, 1997; Harris and Feeny, 2003; Richardson and Lanis, 2007; Chen et al., 2010), other studies argue that high profitability enables firms to employ their resources efficiently to reduce ETR through tax deductions, credits, etc. Moreover, firms with larger pre-tax income may engage in tax avoidance activities to optimize their tax strategies (Manzon and Plesko, 2002; Rego, 2003; Wilson, 2009).

Firm age (AGE) is measured as the natural logarithm of the years in operation for each firm. Kovermann and Wendt (2019) posit that older firms can lower their ETRs due to their longer tax planning experience. However, this longer experience can also enhance companies' public image awareness, potentially increasing their tax rates. A dummy variable (PD) is included to control for publicly listed companies, where PD equals 1 for publicly traded firms and 0 otherwise.

Financial leverage (LEV) is proxied by the ratio of total debt to total assets. The impact of financial leverage on corporate tax avoidance is subject to debate in the literature. Some studies suggest that financial leverage negatively affects the corporate tax burden because debt interest is a tax-deductible expense (Richardson and Lanis, 2007; Stamatopoulos et al., 2019). Conversely, other studies argue that financial leverage positively influences the ETR, positing that firms with high marginal tax rates are more inclined to use debt financing (Harris and Feeny, 2003; Janssen, 2005).

The control variable LOSS is used as a proxy for tax loss carryforward, a widely employed control variable in tax avoidance studies. Losses from previous years can reduce a firm's future tax burden (Graham, 1996; Dyreng and Lindsey, 2009; Chen et al., 2010; Heitzman and Lester, 2021). As net operating loss (NOL) carryforward data is unavailable in the SABI database, the study employs the dummy variable LOSS. This dummy variable takes the value 1 when the firm has reported a negative net income in at least one of the previous three years (t-1, t-2, or t-3), and 0 otherwise.

The study also includes control variables related to a firm's international activity. The dummy variable EXP takes the value 1 if the firm reports export activity and 0 otherwise. The variable FSUB indicates the number of foreign subsidiaries held by the firm. Both of these variables account for the influence of international activity on a firm's effective tax burden.

Lastly, we control for a firm's capital, inventory, and intangible asset intensity. Capital intensity (CINT), inventory intensity (SINT), and intangible asset intensity (IINT) are expressed as ratios of fixed assets to total assets, inventory to total assets, and intangible assets to total assets, respectively. The expected relationship between these variables and tax avoidance varies in the literature. Capital intensity is anticipated to positively correlate with tax avoidance due to the offsetting of fixed asset depreciation against future profits (Janssen, 2005; Richardson and Lanis, 2007; Stamatopoulos et al., 2019). Similarly, intangible asset intensity is expected to positively correlate with tax avoidance as research and development (R&D) expenditure is tax-deductible (Lanis and Richardson, 2012). In contrast, the relationship between inventory intensity and ETR remains inconclusive. Some studies suggest that

inventory-intensive firms should have higher ETRs as inventory intensity serves as a substitute for capital intensity (Zimmerman, 1983; Gupta and Newberry, 1997). However, recent works present an inverse relationship (Stamatopoulos et al., 2019). Additionally, the study includes industry control variables based on the 2-digit NACE classification, covering 87 sectors.

Furthermore, our study incorporates regional control variables. The political orientation of governing parties in different autonomous communities of Spain is controlled using the dummy variable RW that takes the value 1 for right-wing parties and 0 for left-wing parties. In regions without tax autonomy, the political orientation of the central government is considered, while the political orientation of the regional government is considered in foral territories. Left-wing governments are generally expected to be associated with a higher tax burden (Imbeau et al., 2001; Reed, 2006). The STR prevailing each year in both foral and common territory is also controlled for, following Rego (2003), Jaafar and Thornton (2015), and Stamatopoulos et al. (2019), among others.

Additionally, we control whether the firm is situated in the Canary Islands, Ceuta, or Melilla by the dummy variable SZ. These Spanish regions, while subject to the corporate tax regulations of the common territory, enjoy preferential tax rules owing to their distinct geographic positioning.

To reduce the impact of outliers and enhance result reliability, we apply winsorization to all continuous variables in our study at the 1st and 99th percentiles. Consequently, data points below the 1st percentile are adjusted to the value at the 1st percentile, while data points above the 99th percentile are adjusted to the value at the 99th percentile.

Finally, the study includes year fixed effects (FE) to control for time-specific factors that could potentially affect tax avoidance. Appendix B presents the definitions of all the variables.

5. Sample description

Our sample comprises 119,234 observations from 16,421 unique Spanish firms. The data covers the period from 2007 to 2016. We primarily rely on the SABI database, which provides comprehensive financial and ownership structure data. However, it is important to note that certain variables such as group affiliation, ownership concentration, the listing status, and the location of the firm's registered office in a region with tax autonomy have limited historical data availability within the database. To address this limitation, we obtained data from the various versions of SABI available at each year-end between 2007 and 2016. Inactive firms, observations with missing values for any of the variables used, and firms with assets below 3,000 euros were excluded from the analysis. Similarly, firms lacking data for a minimum of 5 consecutive years were also excluded. A detailed description of the data screening process is provided in Appendix C.

Information regarding the political orientation of governing parties in Spanish regions during the analysed period was sourced from the Spanish Senate website (2019), while data concerning the STR for each territory was obtained from the respective tax regulations.

Table 1 provides an overview of the entire dataset. Panel A shows the geographical distribution across Spanish regions. Notably, Catalonia stands out, representing more than one-fifth of the observations (23.84%), followed by the Valencian Community and the Community of Madrid, both of which are significant business centres in Spain. Panel B reveals a consistently even distribution of observations across the years.

And Panel C depicts the sample's stratification by company size. Nearly 93% of the observations pertain to SMEs reporting revenues of €43 million or less. Furthermore, 37.57% represent microenterprises with revenues of €2 million or less.

<Insert Table 1 here.>

Table 2 provides summary statistics for the selected variables. The mean annual ETR is computed at 19.86%, with a slightly higher 3-year ETR of 20.09%. Additionally, the averages of the ratios comparing the effective and statutory tax rates (ETR/STR and ETR3Y/STR3Y) closely hover around 67%. The average firm size, measured by total assets, amounts to €26 million. The mean age of the firms in the sample is 21.7 years, while the average Return on Assets (ROA) is 7.4%. Main shareholders hold a 68.81% stake in these firms on average. Approximately 0.2% of the firms are publicly listed, and 25% are part of business groups. Most of the observations correspond to firms situated in regions governed by right-wing parties during the 2007-2016 period, while nearly 5% of the firms fall under foral territories.

<Insert Table 2 here.>

Table 3 presents the Pearson correlations of all variables, along with the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) of the explanatory variables. Among our explanatory variables, the correlation coefficient between STR and RW exhibits the highest absolute value (-0.44). However, all VIF values are below the threshold for multicollinearity generally set at 5 or 10, depending on the authors (James et al., 2013). Therefore, there appears to be no issue of multicollinearity among the explanatory variables.

<Insert Table 3 here.>

The correlation table unveils a statistically significant negative correlation between the firm's registered office being situated in a foral territory (BCD, NAD) and all tax avoidance proxies (ETR, ETR3Y, ETR/STR, and ETR3Y/STR3Y). In contrast, there exists a positive and significant correlation between our four tax burden metrics and firm size (SIZE) as well as group affiliation (GD).

Furthermore, the correlation table indicates that firms with higher ownership concentration (OC), longer seniority (AGE), higher profitability (ROA), listing on the stock exchange (PD), and greater international activity (EXP and FSUB) face lower tax avoidance. Conversely, all tax burden metrics are negatively correlated with the firm's losses in previous years (LOSS), intangible assets (IINT), capital (CINT), and inventory (SINT) intensity, debt ratio (LEV), and the firm's location in special zones of the common territory (SZ). Notably, group-affiliated firms tend to be larger (SIZE), with more concentrated ownership in the hands of the main shareholder (OC).

The correlation coefficients between STR and ETR, as well as ETR3Y, exhibit a positive and statistically significant relationship. In contrast, STR is negatively correlated with both effective versus statutory tax avoidance ratios (ETR/STR and ETR3Y/STR3Y). This implies that elevated STRs may contribute to higher ETRs, but at the same time, they facilitate the greater prominence of additional tax advantages, such as deductions, in reducing the ratio between effective and statutory rates.

6. Data analysis

We estimate the dynamic model for each of the four metrics we have chosen as a proxy for the dependent variable 'tax avoidance' (ETR, ETR3Y, ETR/STR, and ETR3Y/STR3Y) using the system generalized method of moments (GMM) estimator developed by Arellano and Bover (1995) and Blundell and Bond (1998). The system GMM helps mitigate the endogeneity problem arising when the error term is correlated with any of the explanatory variables. Furthermore, it allows us to control for a firm's individual heterogeneity. We adopt the two-step estimation procedure with finite-sample corrected standard errors, as proposed by Windmeijer (2005). This method provides less biased coefficient estimates and more accurate standard errors. To treat all variables as endogenous covariates, we employ the lagged first differences of the explanatory variables as instruments for the equation in levels and the lagged values of the explanatory variables in levels as instruments for the equation in differences (Arellano and Bover, 1995; Blundell and Bond, 1998). Moreover, to address the issues of heteroscedasticity detected in our panel data when computing the Greene Likelihood Ratio Panel Heteroscedasticity Test, we utilize robust standard errors.

Table 4 presents the results that allow us to test our hypotheses. For each of the four dependent variables, we first estimate the regression without including the interaction term SIZE×GD, and subsequently, we include this interaction term to test hypothesis H4. Columns 1 and 2 display the estimates for the annual ETR; columns 3 and 4 for the 3-year ETR; columns 5 and 6 for the ETR/STR ratio; and columns 7 and 8 for the ETR3Y/STR3Y ratio. Columns 5 to 8 exclude the control variable STR as this variable is incorporated into the calculation of the dependent variable. All estimations include year and industry fixed effects.

<Insert Table 4 here.>

Drawing upon the findings presented in Table 4, we observe that the coefficients of BCD and NAD consistently exhibit a statistically significant negative correlation in all columns. The coefficients in columns 1 to 4 indicate that the ETR faced in foral territories is lower than that in common territory. Besides, the coefficients in columns 5 to 8 reveal that, compared to firms in common territory, those located in foral territory present lower ETR/STR and ETR3Y/STR3Y. This denotes that firms located in foral territories benefit from additional tax advantages beyond their corporate STR, including deductions, exemptions, and other incentives. These results support our hypothesis H1, as firms located in foral territories experience a lower tax burden than those situated in common territory and suggest the existence of tax competition between territories.

The SIZE coefficient displays a positive and statistically significant relationship across all columns. This aligns with previous research by Zimmerman (1983), Moreno-Rojas et al. (2017), Belz et al. (2019), Stamatopoulos et al. (2019), and Granados et al. (2022), indicating that larger firms are less inclined to engage in tax avoidance activities and tend to bear a higher tax burden. Consequently, this supports hypothesis H2. Additionally, the GD coefficient exhibits a positive and highly significant association in all columns. This indicates that group-affiliated firms experience higher tax burden, providing evidence in favour of hypothesis H3.

In columns 2, 4, 6, and 8, we examine the moderating effect of group affiliation on the relationship between firm size and tax avoidance. The coefficient of the interaction between SIZE and GD, representing the incremental effect for group-affiliated firms, is negative and statistically significant in all cases, supporting hypothesis H4. These findings suggest that the positive correlation between firm size and tax burden is attenuated for group-affiliated firms compared to independent firms. Figure 1 illustrates the significant interactions in columns 2, 4, 6, and 8 of Table 4, depicted in panels A, B, C, and D, respectively. The interactions are displayed for the 10th to 90th percentiles of the logarithm of assets, taken in 10-unit increments. At each of these selected points on the X-axis, the model's estimated mean value for the dependent variable and its 95% confidence interval are displayed, both for group-affiliated and independent firms.

<Insert Figure 1 here.>

Upon examining all panels in Figure 1, we observe that group-affiliated firms face lower tax avoidance than independent firms, particularly in the smaller size ranges. However, the slope of the line associated with group-affiliated firms (Panel A: $b=0.346$ (0.199); Panel B: $b=1.363$ (0.000); Panel C: $b=1.228$ (0.128); and Panel D: $b=5.012$ (0.000)) is smaller than the slope of the line associated with independent firms (Panel A: $b=1.096$ (0.000); Panel B: $b=2.600$ (0.000); Panel C: $b=3.725$ (0.000); and Panel D: $b=8.839$ (0.000)) and these differences in slopes are statistically significant. The coefficient of the interaction SIZE×GD indicates the difference between these slopes. These results suggest that the positive slope between firm size and tax burden diminishes or may even approach zero for group-

affiliated firms. Consequently, it appears that group affiliation mitigates the differences in tax avoidance activities conducted by larger and smaller firms.

Regarding the control variables, in line with Janssen (2005), Richardson and Lanis (2007), and Stamatopoulos et al. (2019), the coefficients of CINT and SINT are negative and statistically significant in all columns. This suggests that companies with higher capital and inventory intensity exhibit higher tax avoidance. Furthermore, the negative and significant coefficients of AGE and EXP variables indicate that older firms or those engaged in exporting activities bear a lower tax burden. Similarly, the negative coefficients observed in all columns for LOSS, LEV, and SZ variables indicate that experiencing previous losses, having higher financial leverage, or being located in special zones of the common territory also lead to a reduction in the tax bill.

In contrast, the coefficients for ROA are positive and statistically significant in 6 out of 8 columns, suggesting that the most profitable firms tend to experience a higher tax burden. This outcome aligns with the research of Gupta and Newberry (1997), Harris and Feeny (2003), Richardson and Lanis (2007), and Chen et al. (2010). It is noteworthy that the STR coefficient is positive in columns 1 to 4. As expected, this suggests that higher statutory taxes lead to higher effective taxes.

The coefficients of the lagged dependent variables are consistently positive and significant across all columns, indicating the persistence of the tax burden over time. However, some of the other control variables (OC, PD, RW, FSUB, and IINT) exhibit non-significant coefficients in several regressions.

7. Robustness checks

To ensure the robustness of our findings, this subsection presents additional analyses that test the consistency of our results.

First, we replicated our main analysis using a subsample of firms with revenues equal to or less than €7 million. The objective was to validate hypothesis H1 by focusing on firms that are exclusively taxed according to the fiscal regulations of the territory in which their registered office is located. To achieve this, we excluded from the analysis firms with revenues exceeding €7 million which, as explained in section 2, may be subject to fiscal regulation (either foral or common) that does not correspond with the location of their registered office. In this subsample, we did not include the control variable PD due to the limited number of observations of listed firms.

<Insert Table 5 here.>

Table 5 presents the results following a structure similar to our baseline analysis (Table 4). It is noteworthy that hypothesis H1 is strongly supported when firms are taxed solely in the region where their registered office is located and in accordance with the tax legislation of that territory, as evidenced

by the significantly negative coefficients for BCD and NAD. Furthermore, the remaining results provide further confirmation of hypotheses H2, H3, and H4.

Second, we assess the consistency of our findings by reducing the minimum ownership threshold required to define a business group from over 50% to over 20% (La Porta et al., 1999). We applied the group identification algorithm using this new threshold for the period from 2007 to 2016 and replicated all the multivariate analyses presented earlier. The results obtained continue to support all the hypotheses examined in our study. Furthermore, these results remain robust when we exclude observations from the years 2007 and 2008 to focus on the post-financial crisis period, as well as when we exclude listed companies. While these additional findings are not included in the paper, they can be provided upon request.

Third, to mitigate potential biases stemming from the smaller sample size of firms in foral territories compared to those in the common territory, we conducted a multivariate analysis replication using a matched subsample. This subsample was carefully constructed to include homogeneous groups of firms from both regions. We employed the Propensity Score Matching (PSM) procedure to create this matched sample, seeking to identify pairs of similar firm-year observations. Initially, a logit analysis was performed to calculate the propensity score for each observation in the overall sample. The dependent variables for the logit analyses were BCD and NAD, and they included all other independent and control variables used in the baseline analysis. Subsequently, for each observation in the treatment group, we identified a corresponding observation in the control group from the same year and industry with the closest propensity score. This matching procedure resulted in a matched subsample comprising 11,288 observations, evenly distributed between the treatment and control groups. Finally, we replicated our baseline analyses using this matched subsample, and the results are shown in Table 6.

<Insert Table 6 here.>

The results indicate that the estimated coefficients for BCD and NAD consistently maintain their negative and statistically significant values across all columns. This additional analysis reinforces the evidence that, when comparing similar firms from “foral” and “common” territories, the former experience a lower corporate tax burden than the latter. As a result, hypothesis H1 is once again validated. Furthermore, the estimated coefficients for SIZE are positive and statistically significant in all columns, providing further support for hypotheses H2. Additionally, the coefficient for GD remains positive and significant, while the coefficients for the interaction between SIZE and GD consistently exhibit negative and significant values. These findings provide additional validation for hypotheses H3 and H4.

8. Discussion and conclusions

This paper investigates the relationship between regional tax autonomy, firm size, group affiliation, and tax avoidance, using a dataset of 119,234 observations from 16,421 Spanish firms spanning 2007 to 2016.

Our analysis confirms the first hypothesis (H1), positing that firms within foral territories enjoying tax autonomy bear a lesser corporate tax burden than those in common territories. This aligns with the insights of Bucovetsky (1991), Wilson (1991), and Vandenbussche et al. (2005), who support the notion of horizontal tax competition among regions, demonstrating that peripheral regions tend to extend more significant fiscal benefits to businesses than central regions. This finding not only advances the descriptive work of Romero et al. (2009) and Granados et al. (2021) on regional tax avoidance differences in Spain but also marks the first empirical multivariate analysis within the Spanish context to show significant tax burden disparities between firms in foral and common territories. This multivariate method allowed us to control for several firm- and territory-specific factors recognized as pivotal determinants of tax avoidance, thus minimizing endogeneity, and enhancing the robustness of our results. In agreement with Vandenbussche et al. (2005), we further observed that beyond STRs, additional fiscal incentives like deductions critically influence tax competition among territories.

Our findings also support hypotheses 2 and 3, affirming that larger firms (H2) and those within business groups (H3) engage in less tax avoidance. This phenomenon corroborates that within Spain's institutional framework, both firm size and group affiliation wield comparable impacts on tax avoidance strategies, indicating that the reputational risks associated with fiscal scandals generally surpass the potential gains from aggressive tax practices. This observation reinforces the political cost theory, supported by international studies by Richardson and Lanis (2007), Belz et al. (2019), and Stamatopoulos et al. (2019), and Spanish-centric research by Calvé et al. (2005), Granados et al. (2021, 2022), and Bona-Sánchez et al. (2023). However, this contrasts with other Spanish-focused studies, such as those by Fernández-Rodríguez et al. (2019), Bona-Sánchez et al. (2019), and Castillo-Murciego and López-Laborda (2022), which endorse the political power theory by illustrating large firms' capabilities to mitigate their tax liabilities through mechanisms like former politicians' board involvement or profit shifting to low-tax jurisdictions.

Many preceding studies examining the political cost and power theories in Spain utilized partial samples limited to specific types of firms, such as listed companies (Fernández-Rodríguez, 2004; Bona-Sánchez et al., 2019; Barbera et al., 2020; Castillo-Murciego and López-Laborda, 2022; Bona-Sánchez et al., 2023), cooperatives (Molina, 2012; Martínez et al., 2015) or those in certain sectors (Moreno-Rojas et al., 2017; Granados et al., 2022) or regions (Calvé et al., 2005). We believe that such sampling might have influenced their outcomes. Consequently, our research offers a more representative analysis of

Spain's corporate environment by examining a broad, multisectoral dataset predominantly comprised of SMEs, including both listed and unlisted firms across varied legal forms.

Moreover, our study confirms the fourth hypothesis (H4) by showing that affiliation with a business group significantly alleviates the negative impact of firm size on tax avoidance. This novel moderating effect suggests that small firms within business groups experience tax burdens comparable to those of larger firms. This finding implies that, in terms of tax avoidance, small firms within groups are subject to similar challenges as larger firms, such as greater visibility and public scrutiny or heightened demands for social responsibility (Morck and Nakamura, 1999; Kim et al., 2004; Dewenter et al., 2001; Morck et al., 2005). To mitigate potential reputational damage that could adversely impact the group's value and performance, group affiliated firms will avoid fiscal scandals regardless of their size (Graham et al., 2014; Hanlon and Slemrod, 2019; Baudot et al., 2020). This concern for reputation may motivate all firms within the group to adopt responsible tax behaviours aligned with the group's corporate culture and dynamics (Graham et al., 2014).

Our contributions to the academic literature are manifold. First, this study introduces fresh empirical evidence supporting the theory of horizontal tax competition between foral and common territories in Spain. It represents the first research effort that, surpassing previous descriptive approaches, employs a multivariate analysis to demonstrate that foral regions experience lower fiscal pressure than common territory, controlling for the effects of numerous determinants of tax avoidance and highlighting the significant role played in tax competition among territories by additional fiscal benefits that extend beyond statutory rates.

Second, we provide a new empirical validation of the political cost theory within the Spanish context. Unlike most previous studies in Spain, which focus on partial samples of firms (listed, cooperatives, etc.), our approach uses a broad, multisectoral sample dominated by SMEs and encompassing various legal forms, offering a more representative and nuanced view of the Spanish corporate landscape. Furthermore, our research enriches the dialogue on political power and cost theories by illustrating that group affiliation, much like size, influences firms' tax burdens, indicating that in both large firms and those within business groups, the forces of political cost override those of political power.

Third, we contribute a novel insight to the literature on political power and cost theories by demonstrating for the first time that group affiliation moderates the relationship between firm size and tax avoidance. This finding reveals that within group-affiliated firms, the negative impact of size on tax avoidance is mitigated, equalizing the tax burden between small and large firms, and being higher than that of independent small firms. In line with Morck and Nakamura (1999), Kim et al. (2004), Dewenter et al. (2001) and Morck et al. (2005) this moderation effect suggests that integration into a group may prompt small firms to engage in less aggressive tax practices. This shift is likely driven by the significant reputational risks a fiscal scandal could pose to the entire group, fostering more socially responsible

behaviors that align with maintaining a favorable corporate image and enduring public scrutiny comparable to that of larger firms.

These insights carry significant implications for policymakers and corporate executives, providing valuable perspectives on the determinants of tax avoidance, particularly concerning the influence of location, firm size and business group affiliation. Moreover, our findings suggest that granting fiscal autonomy to specific regions within a country can lead to reduced corporate tax burdens, offering crucial considerations for defining a country's territorial financing model or making strategic corporate location decisions.

9. Limitations and further research

The study exhibits certain limitations, including potential endogeneity issues stemming from omitted variables and potential reverse causality between variables. To tackle potential endogeneity, we utilize the system GMM estimator, employ a Propensity Score Matching method, and conduct several regressions.

Another limitation arises when examining horizontal tax competition (hypothesis H1). Due to the lack of more detailed data, we assume that larger firms (with revenues over €7 million) pay their taxes according to the tax rules of the territory where their registered office is located. However, depending on the percentage of operations they conduct in different territories, these companies may be subject to tax laws (either foral or common) that do not correspond to the location of their registered office. To address this limitation, we recalculate our estimates without these firms, and the results closely resemble those from our original equation. However, we must be cautious in extending the validation of hypothesis H1 to larger firms.

Furthermore, a limitation persists in the dependent variable used to proxy tax avoidance. While commonly employed in the literature, ETR fails to reflect tax strategies that defer taxes, does not identify deliberate tax avoidance activities, and focuses on nonconforming tax strategies (Hanlon and Heitzman, 2010; Badertscher et al., 2019). To partly mitigate these limitations, we employ three alternative tax avoidance proxies that show robust results (ETR3Y, ETR/STR, and ETR3Y/STR3Y).

Looking ahead, future research could expand on the relationship between firm size, group affiliation, and tax avoidance by replicating the study in different contexts, such as countries with varying levels of development and equality. This would provide further insights into the interplay between the theories of political cost and political power. Additionally, further investigation could delve into the mechanisms underlying the relationship between regional tax autonomy and the tax burden on firms, extending the study to other countries with internal horizontal tax competition between territories.

References:

- Adhikari, A., Derashid, C., & Zhang, H. (2006). Public policy, political connections, and effective tax rates: Longitudinal evidence from Malaysia. *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, 25(5), 574-595.
- Arellano, M. & Bover, O. (1995). Another look at the instrumental variable estimation of error-components models. *Journal of Econometrics*, 68, 29–51.
- Badertscher, B.A., Katz, S.P., Rego, S.O., & Wilson, R.J. (2019). Conforming Tax Avoidance and Capital Market Pressure. *The Accounting Review*, 94(6), 1–30.
- Bao, D.H. & Romeo, G.C. (2013). Tax Avoidance and Corporations in the United States—The Effective Tax Rate Abnormality for the Top Five Percent by Corporate Size. *Journal of Applied Business and Economics*, 14(4), 88-100.
- Barbera, A., Merello, P., & Molina, R. (2020). Determinants of corporate effective tax rates: evidence from the euro area. *Academia Revista Latinoamericana de Administración*, 33(3/4), 427-444.
- Baudot, L., Johnson, J.A., Roberts, A., & Roberts, R.W. (2020). Is Corporate Tax Aggressiveness a Reputation Threat? Corporate Accountability, Corporate Social Responsibility, and Corporate Tax Behavior. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 163,197-215.
- Belz, T., Hagen, D.V., & Steffens, C. (2019). Taxes and firm size: Political cost or political power? *Journal of Accounting Literature*, 42(1), 1-28.
- Besley, T.J. & Rosen, H.S. (1998). Vertical Tax Externalities in Tax Setting: Evidence from Gasoline and Cigarettes. *NBER Working Paper*, No. 6.517, National Bureau of Economic Research, Cambridge, MA.
- Beuselinck, C. & Deloof, M. (2014). Earnings Management in Business Groups: Tax Incentives or Expropriation Concealment? *The International Journal of Accounting*, 49, 27–52.
- Blouin, J. & Robinson, L. A. (2020). Double counting accounting: How much profit of multinational enterprises is really in tax havens? Available at SSRN 3491451.
- Blundell, R. W. & Bond, S. R. (1998). Initial conditions and moment restrictions in dynamic panel data models. *Journal of Econometrics*, 87, 115–143.
- Bona-Sánchez, C., Pérez-Alemán, J., & Santana, D.J. (2019). Political ties and corporate tax burden in Spain. *Spanish Journal of Finance and Accounting / Revista Española de Financiación y Contabilidad*, 49(1), 74-93.

- Bona-Sánchez, C., Pérez-Alemán, J., & Santana-Martín, D. J. (2023). Media visibility and corporate social responsibility investment evidence in Spain. *Business Ethics, the Environment & Responsibility*, 32(1), 94-107.
- Brühlhart, M. & Jametti, M. (2006). Vertical versus horizontal tax externalities: An empirical test. *Journal of Public Economics*, 90, 2027–2062.
- Bucovetsky, S. (1991). Asymmetric tax competition. *Journal of Urban Economics*, 30(2), 167-181.
- Calvé, J. I., Labatut, G., & Molina, R. (2005). Variables económico-financieras que inciden sobre la presión fiscal soportada por las empresas de reducida dimensión: Efectos de la Reforma fiscal de 1995 en las empresas de la Comunidad Valenciana. *Revista Española de Financiación y Contabilidad*, 34 (127), 875-897.
- Castillo-Murciego, Á., & López-Laborda, J. (2022). Which multinationals can escape high Statutory Tax Rates? The Profit-Shifting strategy to reduce taxes. *Applied Economics Letters*, 1-5.
- Chen, S., Chen, X., Cheng, Q., & Shevlin, T. (2010). Are family firms more tax aggressive than non-family firms? *Journal of Financial Economics*, 95(1), 41–61.
- Christensen, D.M., Kenchington, D.G., & Laux, R.C. (2022). How do most low ETR firms avoid paying taxes? *Review of Accounting Studies*, 27, 570–606.
- Da Costa, R.H., Tatiwa, R., & Kloeckner, R. (2015). Vertical tax competition in Brazil: Empirical evidence for ICMS and IPI in the period 1995–2009. *Economía*, 16, 111–127.
- Delgado, F., Fernández, E., & Martínez, A. (2014). Effective tax rates in corporate taxation: a quantile regression for the EU. *Inzinerine Ekonomika-Engineering Economics*, 25(5), 487-496.
- Delgado, J.F., Fernández-Rodríguez, E., & Martínez-Arias, A. (2018). Corporation effective tax rates and company size: evidence from Germany. *Economic research-Ekonomska istraživanja*, 31(1), 2081-2099.
- Derashid, C. & Zhang, H. (2003). Effective tax rates and the 'industrial policy' hypothesis: evidence from Malaysia. *Journal of International Accounting, Auditing and Taxation*, 12(1), 45-62.
- Dewenter, K., Novaes, W., & Pettway, R.H. (2001). Visibility versus Complexity in Business Groups: Evidence from Japanese Keiretsu. *The Journal of Business*, 74(1), 79-100.
- Dyreng, S., Hanlon, M., & Maydew, E. (2008). Long-run Corporate Tax Avoidance. *The Accounting Review*, 83(1), 61-82.

- Dyreng, S.D. & Lindsey, B.P. (2009). Using financial accounting data to examine the effect of foreign operations located in tax havens and other countries on U.S. multinational firms' tax rates. *Journal of Accounting Research*, 47(5), 1283-1316.
- Faccio, M. & Lang, L.H. (2002). The ultimate ownership of Western European corporations. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 65(3), 365-395.
- Fernández-Rodríguez, E. (2004). Los factores condicionantes de la presión fiscal empresarial española a partir de la información contable. Especial mención a las decisiones financieras. *Spanish Journal of Finance and Accounting/Revista Española de Financiación y Contabilidad*, 33(120), 125-159.
- Fernández-Rodríguez, E., García-Fernández, R., & Martínez-Arias, A. (2019). Influence of ownership structure on the determinants of effective tax rates of Spanish companies. *Sustainability*, 11(5), 1441.
- Fox, W.F., Hill, B.C., & Murray, M.N. (2015). Vertical competition, horizontal competition, and mobile capital: an empirical investigation. *Public Finance Review*, 43(4), 431-457.
- Goodspeed, T.J. (2000). Tax structure in a federation. *Journal of Public Economics*, 75(3), 493-506.
- Graham, J.R. (1996). Debt and the marginal tax rate. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 41(1), 41-73.
- Graham, J.R., Hanlon, M., Shevlin, T.J., & Shroff, N. (2014). Incentives for tax planning and avoidance: Evidence from the field. *The Accounting Review*, 89(3), 991-1023.
- Gramlich, J. D., Limpaphayom, P., & Rhee, S.G. (2004). Taxes, keiretsu affiliation, and income shifting. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 37(2), 203-228.
- Granados, A.P., Montero, P.A., & Hierro, L.A. (2021). Determinantes de la presión fiscal de las empresas societarias españolas por el impuesto de sociedades durante la crisis económica (2008-2015): Determinants of the tax burden of the Spanish companies for the corporate income tax during the economic crisis (2008-2015). *Revista de Contabilidad-Spanish Accounting Review*, 24(2), 184-201.
- Granados, A.P., Montero, P.A., & Hierro, L.A. (2022). Do tourist companies support a greater direct tax burden? The case of Spain. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 25(4), 579-591.
- Granovetter, M. (2005). Business groups and social organization. In N. J. Smelser & R. Swedburg (eds.), *The handbook of economic sociology*, 2nd edition, Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Gupta, S. & Newberry, K. (1997). Determinants of the variability in corporate effective tax rates: Evidence from longitudinal data. *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, 16(1), 1-34.
- Guenther, D.A., Matsunaga, S. & Williams, B. (2013). Tax Avoidance, Tax Aggressiveness, Tax Risk and Firm Risk. *Working paper*, University of Oregon, Eugene, OR, August.

- Guillén, M. F. (2000). Business groups in emerging economies: A resource-based view. *Academy of Management Journal*, 43(3), 362-380.
- Hanlon, M. & Heitzman, S. (2010). A review of tax research. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 50(2/3), 127-178.
- Hanlon, M. & Slemrod, J. (2009). What does tax aggressiveness signal? Evidence from stock price reactions to news about tax shelter involvement. *Journal of Public Economics*, 93, 126-141.
- Hansson, A. & Olofsdotter, A. (2005). Integration and Tax Competition: An Empirical Study of OECD Countries. *Lund University Working Paper*, No. 2005/04.
- Harris, M.N. & Feeny, S. (2003). Habit persistence in effective tax rates. *Applied Economics*, 35(8), 951-958.
- Hayashi, M. & Boadway, R. (2001). An Empirical Analysis of Intergovernmental Tax Interaction: The Case of Business Income Taxes in Canada. *The Canadian Journal of Economics / Revue Canadienne D'Economique*, 34(2), 481-503.
- Heitzman, S. & Lester, R. (2021). Tax Loss Measurement. *National Tax Journal*, 74(4), 867–893.
- Hsu, W.H & Liu, H.T. (2018). Tax Avoidance and Pyramidal Layers. *NTU Management Review*, 28(1), 1-42.
- Imbeau, L.M., Pétry, F., & Lamari, M. (2001). Left-right party ideology and government policies: A meta-analysis. *European Journal of Political Research*, 40, 1–29.
- Jaafar, A. & Thornton, J. (2015). Tax Havens and Effective Tax Rates: An Analysis of Private versus Public European Firms. *The International Journal of Accounting*, 50(4), 435-457.
- James, G., Witten, D., Hastie, T., & Tibshirani, R. (eds.). (2013). *An introduction to statistical learning: with applications in R*. New York: Springer.
- Janssen, B. (2005). Corporate Effective Tax Rates in the Netherlands. *De Economist*, 153, 47–66.
- Jensen, M.C. & Meckling, W.H. (1976). Theory of the firm: Managerial behavior, agency costs and ownership structure. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 3(4), 305-360.
- Jung, K., Kim, B., & Kim, B. (2009). Tax motivated income shifting and Korean business groups (chaebol). *Journal of Business Finance and Accounting*, 36(5/6), 552-586.
- Kang, J. Y. & Kim, J. S. (2021). International Diversification, Tax Avoidance, and Chaebol: Evidence from Korea. *Journal of Korea Trade*, 25(5), 74-92.

- Keen, M.J. & Kotsogiannis, C. (2002). Does Federalism Lead to Excessively High Taxes? *American Economic Review*, 92(1), 363-370.
- Keen, M. (2008). Tax Competition. In: Palgrave Macmillan (eds.) *The New Palgrave Dictionary of Economics*, Palgrave Macmillan, London.
- Khanna, T. & Palepu, K. (1999). Policy shocks, market intermediaries, and corporate strategy: The evolution of business groups in Chile and India. *Journal of Economics & Management Strategy*, 8(2), 271-310.
- Khanna, T. & Yafeh, Y. (2007). Business groups in emerging markets: Paragons or parasites? *Journal of Economic Literature*, 45(2), 331-372.
- Kim, H., Hoskisson, R.E., & Wan, W.P. (2004). Power dependence, diversification strategy, and performance in keiretsu member firms. *Strategic Management Journal*, 25(7), 613-636.
- Kovermann, J. & Wendt, M. (2019). Tax Avoidance in Family Firms: Evidence from Large Private Firms. *Journal of Contemporary Accounting and Economics*, 15(2), 145-157.
- Landry, S., Deslandes, M., & Fortin, A. (2013). Tax Aggressiveness, Corporate Social Responsibility, and Ownership Structure. *Journal of Accounting, Ethics and Public Policy*, 14(3), 611-645.
- Lanis, R. & Richardson, G. (2012). Corporate social responsibility and tax aggressiveness: An empirical analysis. *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, 31(1), 86-108.
- La Porta, R., Lopez-de-Silanes, F., Shleifer, A., & Vishny, R. W. (1999). Investor protection: origins, consequences, and reform. *NBER Working Papers 7428*, National Bureau of Economic Research, Inc.
- Locorotondo, R., Dewaelheyns, N., & Van Hulle, C. (2012). The consequences of business group affiliation: a review of the literature. *Review of Business and Economic Literature*, 57(1), 77-97.
- Manzon, G.B., & Plesko, G.A. (2002). The relation between financial and tax reporting measures of income. *Tax Law Review*, 55, 175-214.
- Martínez, J., Ibáñez, P.C., & Campillo, J.P. (2015). La presión fiscal en las cooperativas: una valoración por tamaños, comunidades y sectores para el período 2008-2011. *REVESCO. Revista de Estudios Cooperativos*, 119, 132-158.
- Mills, L. & Newberry, K. (2004). Do foreign multinationals' tax incentives influence their US income and reporting debt policy? *National Tax Journal*, 57(1), 89-107.
- Molina, R. (2012). La presión fiscal en las cooperativas españolas durante el período 2003-2008. *CIRIEC-España, Revista de Economía Pública, Social y Cooperativa*, 74, 39-58.

- Molina, R., & Barberá, A. (2017). Los determinantes de la presión fiscal empresarial: evidencia en las empresas de la zona euro durante el período 2004-2014. *Harvard Deusto Business Research*, 6(1), 69-82.
- Monterrey, J., Sánchez, A., & Fernández, E. (2010). Diferencias en agresividad fiscal entre empresas familiares y no familiares. *Spanish Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 39, 65-107.
- Morck, R. & Nakamura, M. (1999). Banks and Corporate Control in Japan. *The Journal of Finance*, 54(1), 319–339.
- Morck, R. & Yeung, B.Y. (2004). Special issues relating to corporate governance and family control. Available at SSRN 625283.
- Morck, R., Wolfenzon, D., & Yeung, B. (2005). Corporate governance, economic entrenchment, and growth. *Journal of Economic Literature*, 43(3), 655-720.
- Moreno-Rojas, J., González-Rodríguez, M. R., & Martín-Samper, R. C. (2017). Determinants of the effective tax rate in the tourism sector. A dynamic Panel Data Model. *Tourism & Management Studies*, 13(3), 31-38.
- OECD (2023). Government at a Glance 2023, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/3d5c5d31-en>.
- Overesch, M. & Rincke, J. (2011). What Drives Corporate Tax Rates Down? A Reassessment of Globalization, Tax Competition, and Dynamic Adjustment to Shocks. *The Scandinavian Journal of Economics*, 113(3), 579-602.
- Plesko, G.A. (2003). An Evaluation of Alternative Measures of Corporate Tax Rates. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 35, 201–226.
- Porcano, T. M. (1986). Corporate Tax Rates: Progressive, Proportional or Regressive. *The Journal of the American Taxation Association*, 7(2), 17-31.
- Reed, R. (2006). Democrats, Republicans, and Taxes: Evidence That Political Parties Matter. *Journal of Public Economics*, 90, 725–750.
- Rego, S.O. (2003). Tax-Avoidance Activities of U.S. Multinational Corporations. *Contemporary Accounting Research*, 20(4), 805–833.
- Richardson, G. & Lanis, R. (2007). Determinants of the Variability in Corporate Effective Tax Rates and Tax Reform: Evidence from Australia. *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, 26, 689-704.

- Romero, E., Molina, R., & Labatut, G. (2009). La presión fiscal en las empresas españolas: un estudio de las diferencias entre comunidades autónomas y sus efectos sobre las empresas de reducida dimensión. *Revista Internacional de la Pequeña y Mediana Empresa*, 1(2), 78-96.
- Sánchez-Marín, G., Portillo-Navarro, M.J., & Clavel, J.G. (2016). The influence of family involvement on tax aggressiveness of family firms. *Journal of Family Business Management*, 6(2), 143-168.
- Schaffer, M.E. & Turley, G. (2001). Effective versus statutory taxation: measuring effective tax administration in transition economies. *European Bank for Reconstruction and Development Working Paper*, 62.
- Siegfried, J. (1972). *The relationship between economic structure and the effect of political influence: empirical evidence from the federal corporation income tax program*. Ph.D. dissertation, University of Wisconsin.
- Spanish Senate (2019). Administración e Instituciones autonómicas: composición de parlamentos y gobiernos. Available at:
http://www.senado.es/web/conocersenado/biblioteca/dossieresareastematicas/detalledossier/index.html?lang=en&id=DOSSIER_CCAA1&parte=CCAA1_PLANES (accessed March 2019).
- Stamatopoulos, I., Hadjidema, S., & Eleftheriou, K. (2019). Explaining corporate effective tax rates: Evidence from Greece. *Economic Analysis and Policy*, 62, 236-254.
- Su, W. & Tan, D. (2018). Business groups and tax havens. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 153, 1067-1081.
- Tobin, G. & Walsh, K. (2013). What makes a country a tax haven? An assessment of international standards shows why Ireland is not a tax haven. *The Economic and Social Review*, 44(3), 401-424.
- Transparency International (2022). <https://www.transparency.org/en/cpi/2022> [Online Resource]
- UNDP (2022). *Human Development Report 2021-22. Uncertain Times, Unsettled Lives: Shaping our Future in a Transforming World*. New York. <https://hdr.undp.org/content/human-development-report-2021-22>
- Vandenbussche, H. & Tan, C. (2005). The Taxation of Multinationals: Firm Level Evidence for Belgium. *LICOS Discussion Paper*, No. 160/2005, 19 September.
- Vandenbussche, H., Crabbé, K., & Janssen, B. (2005). Is there Regional Tax Competition? Firm Level Evidence for Belgium, *De Economist*, 153, 257-276.
- Watts, R.L. & Zimmerman, J. L. (1978). Towards a Positive Theory of the Determination of Accounting Standards. *The Accounting Review*, 53(1), 112-134.

- Watts, R. L. & Zimmerman, J. L. (1986). *Positive Accounting Theory*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice Hill.
- Wilson, J.D. (1986). A theory of interregional tax competition. *Journal of Urban Economics*, 19(3), 296-315.
- Wilson, J.D. (1991). Tax competition with interregional differences in factor endowments. *Regional Science and Urban Economics*, 21(3), 423-451.
- Wilson, J.D. (1999). Theories of tax competition. *National Tax Journal*, 52(2), 269-304.
- Wilson, R.J. (2009). An examination of corporate tax shelter participants. *The Accounting Review*, 84(3), 969-999.
- Windmeijer, F. (2005). A finite sample correction for the variance of linear efficient two-step GMM estimators. *Journal of Econometrics*, 126(1), 25–51.
- Zimmerman, J. L. (1983). Taxes and firm size. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 5, 119-149.
- Zodrow, G.R. & Mieszkowski, P. (1986). Pigou, Tiebout, property taxation, and the underprovision of local public goods. *Journal of Urban Economics*, 19(3), 356-370.

Figure 1: Interaction plot of firm's size and group affiliation

Note: This figure plots the interaction between firm's size and group affiliation. Firm's size is measured by the natural logarithm of total assets. Interactions are shown for the 10th to 90th percentiles of the log of assets, taken in 10-unit increments. For each of these percentiles on the Y-axis, the mean value of the variable measuring tax avoidance is displayed along with its 95% confidence interval. In Panels A, B, C, and D, the vertical axis represents the annual ETR, the 3-year ETR, the annual ETR in relation to the STR, and the 3-year ETR relative to the average statutory rate for the corresponding period. All panels depict the interaction effects as derived from the system GMM models in our baseline analysis.

Table 1: Distribution of observations

Panel A: Distribution per region			
	Freq.	Percentage	Cum.
Andalucia	12,647	10.61	10.61
Aragon	4,497	3.77	14.38
Asturias	2,272	1.91	16.28
Canary Islands	3,307	2.77	19.06
Cantabria	999	0.84	19.90
Castilla y Leon	6,061	5.08	24.98
Castilla-La Mancha	4,734	3.97	28.95
Catalonia	28,424	23.84	52.79
Ceuta	183	0.15	52.94
Valencian Community	15,493	12.99	65.94
Community of Madrid	14,549	12.20	78.14
Extremadura	1,612	1.35	79.49
Galicia	9,574	8.03	87.52
Balearic Islands	2,816	2.36	89.88
La Rioja	1,341	1.12	91.01
Melilla	158	0.13	91.14
Navarre	1,567	1.31	92.45
Basque Country	4,145	3.48	95.93
Region of Murcia	4,855	4.07	100.00
Total	119,234	100.00	

Panel B: Distribution by year			
	Freq.	Percentage	Cum.
2007	7,490	6.28	6.28
2008	8,693	7.29	13.57
2009	10,523	8.83	22.40
2010	12,304	10.32	32.72
2011	14,137	11.86	44.57
2012	14,893	12.49	57.06
2013	14,058	11.79	68.85
2014	13,248	11.11	79.97
2015	12,470	10.46	90.42
2016	11,418	9.58	100.00
Total	119,234	100.00	

Panel C: Distribution by firm size			
	Freq.	Percentage	Cum.
Micro	44,799	37.57	37.57
Small	45,347	38.03	75.60
Medium	20,733	17.39	92.99
Large	8,355	7.01	100.00
Total	119,234	100.00	

Note: The size categories have been determined in accordance with EU Recommendation 2003/361 for the classification of SMEs.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics

	N	Mean	Median	Std. Dev.	Max	Min
ETR	119,234	19.86	20.49	11.08	100.00	0.00
ETR3Y	116,892	20.09	20.86	9.89	99.92	0.00
ETR/STR	119,234	67.48	69.80	36.46	221.23	0.00
ETR3Y/STR3Y	116,892	67.07	69.88	32.82	333.78	0.00
BCD	119,234	0.03	0.00	0.18	1.00	0.00
NAD	119,234	0.01	0.00	0.11	1.00	0.00
SIZE	119,234	15.07	14.94	1.53	18.46	9.55
GD	119,234	0.25	0.00	0.43	1.00	0.00
SZ	119,234	0.03	0.00	0.17	1.00	0.00
OC	119,234	68.81	60.00	28.60	100.00	0.01
ROA	119,234	7.40	5.04	7.48	65.56	0.14
AGE	119,234	2.93	3.00	0.53	3.91	0.69
PD	119,234	0.00	0.00	0.04	1.00	0.00
LOSS	119,234	0.08	0.00	0.27	1.00	0.00
IINT	119,234	2.51	0.30	6.91	56.89	0.00
CINT	119,234	34.48	30.78	23.24	98.91	0.08
SINT	119,234	20.14	15.13	18.72	94.54	0.00
LEV	119,234	55.42	57.25	23.40	193.36	0.90
RW	119,234	0.57	1.00	0.49	1.00	0.00
EXP	119,234	0.33	0.00	0.47	1.00	0.00
FSUB	119,234	0.56	0.00	2.56	17.00	0.00
STR	119,234	29.42	30.00	1.70	32.50	25.00

Note: See Appendix B for a description of these variables.

Table 3: Variance Inflation Factor and Pearson correlation results

Variables	VIF	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)	(13)	(14)	(15)	(16)	(17)	(18)	(19)	(20)	(21)	(22)
(1) ETR		1.00																					
(2) ETR3Y		0.80 ^a	1.00																				
(3) ETR/STR		0.99 ^a	0.80 ^a	1.00																			
(4) ETR3Y/STR3Y		0.80 ^a	1.00 ^a	0.81 ^a	1.00																		
(5) BCD	1.04	-0.03 ^a	-0.03 ^a	-0.04 ^a	-0.03 ^a	1.00																	
(6) NAD	1.01	-0.01 ^a	-0.01 ^a	-0.02 ^a	-0.01 ^a	-0.02 ^a	1.00																
(7) SIZE	1.71	0.22 ^a	0.25 ^a	0.23 ^a	0.25 ^a	0.05 ^a	0.04 ^a	1.00															
(8) GD	1.79	0.22 ^a	0.25 ^a	0.23 ^a	0.25 ^a	0.06 ^a	0.01 ^a	0.44 ^a	1.00														
(9) SZ	1.06	-0.07 ^a	-0.10 ^a	-0.08 ^a	-0.10 ^a	-0.03 ^a	-0.02 ^a	0.03 ^a	-0.02 ^a	1.00													
(10) OC	1.34	0.06 ^a	0.06 ^a	0.07 ^a	0.07 ^a	0.02 ^a	-0.01 ^c	0.04 ^a	0.45 ^a	0.01 ^a	1.00												
(11) ROA	1.18	0.23 ^a	0.27 ^a	0.25 ^a	0.27 ^a	0.04 ^a	0.02 ^a	0.12 ^a	0.21 ^a	0.00	0.09 ^a	1.00											
(12) AGE	1.31	0.09 ^a	0.09 ^a	0.11 ^a	0.11 ^a	0.03 ^a	0.02 ^a	0.34 ^a	0.07 ^a	-0.03 ^a	-0.12 ^a	-0.04 ^a	1.00										
(13) PD	1.01	0.01 ^b	0.01 ^a	0.01 ^b	0.01 ^a	0.03 ^a	0.03 ^a	0.08 ^a	0.00	-0.01 ^b	-0.05 ^a	0.01 ^a	0.05 ^a	1.00									
(14) LOSS	1.02	-0.05 ^a	-0.05 ^a	-0.05 ^a	-0.05 ^a	-0.10 ^a	-0.01 ^a	-0.04 ^a	0.04 ^a	0.01 ^a	0.03 ^a	-0.04 ^a	-0.04 ^a	-0.01 ^b	1.00								
(15) IINT	1.08	-0.02 ^a	-0.02 ^a	-0.03 ^a	-0.03 ^a	-0.01 ^c	-0.02 ^a	0.02 ^a	0.09 ^a	-0.01 ^a	0.05 ^a	0.02 ^a	-0.08 ^a	0.01 ^a	0.03 ^a	1.00							
(16) CINT	1.30	-0.10 ^a	-0.11 ^a	-0.10 ^a	-0.11 ^a	-0.03 ^a	0.00	0.14 ^a	0.00 ^c	0.07 ^a	-0.01 ^a	-0.07 ^a	0.02 ^a	0.03 ^a	0.05 ^a	0.22 ^a	1.00						
(17) SINT	1.32	-0.24 ^a	-0.25 ^a	-0.25 ^a	-0.25 ^a	-0.02 ^a	-0.01 ^a	-0.19 ^a	-0.15 ^a	-0.03 ^a	-0.04 ^a	-0.22 ^a	-0.03 ^a	-0.01 ^a	0.01 ^a	-0.12 ^a	-0.38 ^a	1.00					
(18) LEV	1.21	-0.37 ^a	-0.39 ^a	-0.38 ^a	-0.41 ^a	-0.04 ^a	-0.04 ^a	-0.12 ^a	-0.07 ^a	-0.11 ^a	0.04 ^a	-0.23 ^a	-0.27 ^a	0.00	0.09 ^a	0.05 ^a	-0.04 ^a	0.19 ^a	1.00				
(19) RW	1.31	-0.02 ^a	-0.08 ^a	0.03 ^a	-0.04 ^a	0.03 ^a	0.08 ^a	0.02 ^a	-0.01 ^c	0.14 ^a	0.02 ^a	-0.04 ^a	0.18 ^a	0.00	-0.01 ^a	-0.01 ^a	0.02 ^a	0.02 ^a	-0.13 ^a	1.00			
(20) EXP	1.20	0.05 ^a	0.05 ^a	0.06 ^a	0.05 ^a	0.02 ^a	0.02 ^a	0.35 ^a	0.15 ^a	-0.08 ^a	0.00	0.05 ^a	0.20 ^a	0.04 ^a	-0.02 ^a	-0.04 ^a	-0.10 ^a	0.04 ^a	-0.07 ^a	0.08 ^a	1.00		
(21) FSUB	1.21	0.12 ^a	0.13 ^a	0.13 ^a	0.13 ^a	0.03 ^a	0.02 ^a	0.30 ^a	0.38 ^a	-0.01 ^a	0.17 ^a	0.12 ^a	0.04 ^a	0.03 ^a	0.01 ^b	0.11 ^a	0.05 ^a	-0.10 ^a	-0.01 ^a	0.00	0.09 ^a	1.00	
(22) STR	1.30	0.01 ^b	0.04 ^a	-0.11 ^a	-0.03 ^a	-0.16 ^a	-0.03 ^c	-0.04 ^a	-0.02 ^a	0.01 ^a	-0.02 ^a	0.00	-0.18 ^a	0.00	0.03 ^a	0.05 ^a	0.00	0.00	0.11 ^a	-0.44 ^a	-0.06 ^a	-0.01 ^a	1.00

Note: This table reports pairwise correlations and their significance level among the dependent, independent and control variables. See Appendix B for a description of these variables.

a, b, and c denote statistical significance at the 0.01, 0.05, and 0.10 levels, respectively.

Table 4: Tax avoidance, regional tax autonomy, size and group affiliation

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
Dep. var.	ETR	ETR	ETR3Y	ETR3Y	ETR/STR	ETR/STR	ETR3Y/ STR3Y	ETR3Y/ STR3Y
ETR _{t-1}	0.299 ^a (0.009)	0.301 ^a (0.009)						
ETR3Y _{t-1}			0.238 ^a (0.025)	0.236 ^a (0.024)				
ETR/STR _{t-1}					0.317 ^a (0.009)	0.318 ^a (0.009)		
ETR3Y/STR3Y _{t-1}							0.343 ^a (0.030)	0.342 ^a (0.029)
BCD	-1.115 ^a (0.280)	-1.269 ^a (0.285)	-1.898 ^a (0.400)	-1.859 ^a (0.406)	-2.773 ^b (1.089)	-3.413 ^a (0.954)	-3.385 ^b (1.481)	-3.064 ^b (1.484)
NAD	-2.562 ^a (0.547)	-2.541 ^a (0.549)	-4.040 ^a (0.790)	-3.941 ^a (0.775)	-9.063 ^a (1.882)	-8.725 ^a (1.863)	-12.069 ^a (2.740)	-11.728 ^a (2.686)
SIZE	0.812 ^a (0.136)	1.096 ^a (0.159)	2.394 ^a (0.144)	2.600 ^a (0.168)	3.282 ^a (0.513)	3.864 ^a (0.516)	8.188 ^a (0.543)	8.744 ^a (0.586)
GD	1.482 ^a (0.377)	1.868 ^a (0.677)	1.305 ^a (0.400)	2.433 ^a (0.723)	4.440 ^a (1.433)	4.974 ^a (1.428)	4.418 ^a (1.433)	5.966 ^a (1.519)
SIZE×GD		-0.750 ^b (0.291)		-1.237 ^a (0.265)		-2.711 ^a (0.895)		-3.575 ^a (0.907)
SZ	-4.028 ^a (0.690)	-4.123 ^a (0.693)	-5.722 ^a (1.008)	-5.982 ^a (0.996)	-14.179 ^a (2.251)	-14.272 ^a (2.250)	-19.264 ^a (3.311)	-20.079 ^a (3.267)
OC	0.000 (0.005)	0.001 (0.005)	0.000 (0.005)	0.005 (0.005)	0.004 (0.018)	0.011 (0.017)	0.004 (0.018)	0.019 (0.018)
ROA	0.028 ^a (0.010)	0.023 ^b (0.010)	0.012 ^c (0.007)	0.012 ^c (0.007)	0.146 ^a (0.031)	0.143 ^a (0.031)	0.022 (0.022)	0.019 (0.022)
AGE	-0.863 ^a (0.149)	-0.988 ^a (0.166)	-1.783 ^a (0.184)	-1.716 ^a (0.198)	-3.326 ^a (0.613)	-3.252 ^a (0.509)	-5.736 ^a (0.649)	-5.517 ^a (0.652)
PD	-6.106 ^b (2.553)	-7.007 ^a (2.254)	-3.951 (4.601)	-4.847 (4.323)	-20.515 ^b (8.834)	-21.199 ^a (7.293)	-9.305 (14.400)	-12.227 (13.377)
LOSS	-0.288 ^c (0.165)	-0.285 ^c (0.164)	-0.744 ^a (0.243)	-0.778 ^a (0.243)	-1.008 ^b (0.515)	-1.118 ^b (0.524)	-1.753 ^c (1.043)	-1.856 ^c (1.062)
IINT	-0.015 (0.012)	-0.018 (0.013)	-0.048 ^a (0.016)	-0.047 ^a (0.016)	-0.033 (0.039)	-0.037 (0.041)	-0.050 (0.053)	-0.050 (0.046)
CINT	-0.071 ^a (0.006)	-0.071 ^a (0.006)	-0.061 ^a (0.006)	-0.061 ^a (0.006)	-0.236 ^a (0.020)	-0.229 ^a (0.019)	-0.209 ^a (0.019)	-0.209 ^a (0.019)
SINT	-0.105 ^a (0.007)	-0.107 ^a (0.007)	-0.068 ^a (0.007)	-0.070 ^a (0.007)	-0.352 ^a (0.021)	-0.355 ^a (0.021)	-0.229 ^a (0.023)	-0.233 ^a (0.023)
LEV	-0.125 ^a (0.006)	-0.126 ^a (0.006)	-0.127 ^a (0.006)	-0.127 ^a (0.006)	-0.419 ^a (0.022)	-0.411 ^a (0.019)	-0.421 ^a (0.026)	-0.420 ^a (0.024)
RW	-0.372 ^c (0.222)	-0.331 (0.218)	-0.639 ^a (0.148)	-0.643 ^a (0.147)	-0.228 (0.764)	-0.241 (0.763)	-1.674 ^a (0.494)	-1.655 ^a (0.491)
EXP	-0.449 ^a (0.157)	-0.505 ^a (0.159)	-0.596 ^a (0.151)	-0.587 ^a (0.148)	-1.535 ^a (0.505)	-1.688 ^a (0.505)	-1.728 ^a (0.497)	-1.695 ^a (0.486)
FSUB	-0.051 (0.047)	-0.015 (0.049)	-0.034 (0.065)	0.063 (0.057)	-0.181 (0.162)	-0.009 (0.157)	-0.037 (0.180)	0.222 (0.176)
STR	0.219 ^a (0.085)	0.211 ^b (0.085)	0.120 ^b (0.050)	0.118 ^b (0.050)				
Intercept	8.176 ^b (3.225)	4.469 (3.377)	4.999 ^b (2.306)	8.358 ^a (2.603)	39.299 ^a (6.467)	29.302 ^a (7.284)	8.246 (6.656)	17.757 ^b (7.402)
Year F.E.	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Industry F.E.	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	119,234	119,234	116,892	116,892	119,234	119,234	116,892	116,892

Note: This table reports the coefficients and their corresponding robust standard errors (in parentheses) for eight panel data estimations. All columns show the estimates generated by the system GMM dynamic panel estimator using a two-step estimation procedure, with finite-sample correction applied to variance. The sample in all cases encompasses both group-affiliated and stand-alone firms. In columns 1 and 2, the dependent variable represents the annual ETR, truncated between 0 and 100%. In columns 3 and 4, the dependent variable is the long-term 3-year ETR, similarly bounded. Columns 5 and 6 display the annual ETR relative to the STR, while columns 7 and 8 showcase the 3-year ETR relative to the average STR over the same period. All estimations account for year and industry fixed effects. All columns incorporate observations from firms that have provided data on all variables for a minimum of five consecutive years to assess the absence of second-order serial correlation. For a detailed description of the variables, please refer to Appendix B.

a, b, and c denote statistical significance at the 0.01, 0.05, and 0.10 levels, respectively.

Table 5: Robustness checks

Firms with revenues equal to or less than €7 million								
Dep. var.	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
	ETR	ETR	ETR3Y	ETR3Y	ETR/STR	ETR/STR	ETR3Y/ STR3Y	ETR3Y/ STR3Y
ETR _{t-1}	0.334 ^a (0.012)	0.333 ^a (0.012)						
ETR3Y _{t-1}			0.212 ^a (0.017)	0.211 ^a (0.015)				
ETR/STR _{t-1}					0.350 ^a (0.012)	0.350 ^a (0.012)		
ETR3Y/STR3Y _{t-1}							0.310 ^a (0.020)	0.318 ^a (0.029)
BCD	-1.736 ^a (0.401)	-1.752 ^a (0.400)	-1.683 ^a (0.536)	-1.621 ^a (0.541)	-4.111 ^a (1.289)	-4.191 ^a (1.295)	-3.362 ^c (1.963)	-3.246 ^c (1.959)
NAD	-1.208 ^c (0.620)	-1.261 ^b (0.622)	-2.356 ^b (1.191)	-2.461 ^b (1.206)	-5.628 ^b (2.530)	-5.758 ^b (2.521)	-6.148 ^a (2.158)	-9.349 ^a (2.072)
SIZE	0.354 ^c (0.204)	0.378 ^c (0.215)	1.275 ^a (0.227)	1.449 ^a (0.238)	1.281 ^c (0.709)	1.377 ^c (0.744)	4.586 ^a (0.797)	3.836 ^a (0.834)
GD	1.676 ^a (0.624)	2.248 ^b (0.982)	2.196 ^a (0.565)	2.545 ^b (1.170)	5.233 ^a (1.999)	5.757 ^b (2.715)	7.087 ^a (1.900)	8.540 ^a (2.751)
SIZE×GD		-0.556 ^b (0.274)		-1.157 ^b (0.548)		-1.508 ^c (0.851)		-3.400 ^c (1.932)
SZ	-3.379 ^a (0.780)	-3.468 ^a (0.782)	-4.875 ^a (1.134)	-5.064 ^a (1.127)	-11.283 ^a (2.575)	-11.565 ^a (2.576)	-16.550 ^a (3.786)	-15.317 ^a (3.848)
OC	0.010 ^c (0.006)	0.010 ^c (0.006)	0.000 (0.006)	-0.000 (0.006)	0.038 ^b (0.019)	0.039 ^b (0.019)	0.008 (0.022)	0.012 (0.021)
ROA	0.041 ^a (0.013)	0.042 ^a (0.013)	0.029 ^a (0.009)	0.029 ^a (0.009)	0.197 ^a (0.041)	0.204 ^a (0.040)	0.088 ^a (0.031)	0.133 ^a (0.031)
AGE	-0.952 ^a (0.211)	-0.963 ^a (0.209)	-1.800 ^a (0.252)	-1.875 ^a (0.252)	-3.124 ^a (0.688)	-3.153 ^a (0.677)	-5.939 ^a (0.882)	-5.328 ^a (0.910)
LOSS	-0.264 ^c (0.156)	-0.270 ^c (0.158)	-0.565 ^c (0.292)	-0.571 ^b (0.291)	-1.253 ^b (0.603)	-1.194 ^b (0.598)	-1.793 ^c (1.075)	-1.604 ^c (0.934)
IINT	-0.002 (0.017)	-0.002 (0.016)	-0.056 ^b (0.024)	-0.049 ^b (0.020)	-0.004 (0.053)	-0.010 (0.052)	-0.075 ^c (0.045)	-0.044 (0.043)
CINT	-0.064 ^a (0.007)	-0.062 ^a (0.007)	-0.059 ^a (0.007)	-0.058 ^a (0.007)	-0.220 ^a (0.023)	-0.214 ^a (0.023)	-0.208 ^a (0.023)	-0.191 ^a (0.023)
SINT	-0.109 ^a (0.008)	-0.109 ^a (0.007)	-0.099 ^a (0.008)	-0.099 ^a (0.008)	-0.374 ^a (0.025)	-0.374 ^a (0.024)	-0.345 ^a (0.027)	-0.400 ^a (0.028)
LEV	-0.134 ^a (0.007)	-0.133 ^a (0.007)	-0.149 ^a (0.007)	-0.150 ^a (0.007)	-0.440 ^a (0.025)	-0.437 ^a (0.024)	-0.514 ^a (0.026)	-0.502 ^a (0.031)
RW	-0.408 (0.251)	-0.396 (0.250)	-0.813 ^a (0.208)	-0.797 ^a (0.208)	-0.936 (0.941)	-0.874 (0.939)	-2.169 ^a (0.710)	-2.256 ^a (0.733)
EXP	-0.506 ^a (0.183)	-0.503 ^a (0.183)	-0.505 ^a (0.179)	-0.510 ^a (0.179)	-1.730 ^a (0.601)	-1.717 ^a (0.601)	-1.659 ^a (0.595)	-1.200 ^b (0.598)
FSUB	0.036 (0.114)	0.103 (0.108)	0.290 ^b (0.126)	0.347 ^a (0.116)	0.131 (0.344)	0.319 (0.327)	0.950 ^b (0.415)	1.244 ^a (0.374)
STR	0.201 ^c (0.109)	0.198 ^c (0.112)	0.135 ^c (0.072)	0.144 ^c (0.083)				
Intercept	26.328 ^a (4.740)	25.706 ^a (4.679)	12.300 ^a (3.789)	9.817 ^b (3.963)	85.148 ^a (9.315)	83.547 ^a (9.956)	53.008 ^a (10.153)	60.537 ^a (10.666)
Year F.E.	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Industry F.E.	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	68,348	68,348	66,121	66,121	68,348	68,348	66,121	66,121

Note: This table reports the coefficients and their corresponding robust standard errors (in parentheses) for eight panel data estimations. All columns show the estimates generated by the system GMM dynamic panel estimator using a two-step estimation procedure, with finite-sample correction applied to variance. The sample in all cases includes both group-affiliated and stand-alone firms, and is limited to firms with revenues of €7 million or less. In columns 1 and 2, the dependent variable represents the annual ETR, truncated between 0 and 100%. In columns 3 and 4, the dependent variable is the long-term 3-year ETR, similarly bounded. Columns 5 and 6 display the annual ETR relative to the STR, while columns 7 and 8 showcase the 3-year ETR relative to the average STR over the same period. All estimations account for year and industry fixed effects. All columns incorporate observations from firms that have provided data on all variables for a minimum of five consecutive years to assess the absence of second-order serial correlation. For a detailed description of the variables, please refer to Appendix B.

a, b, and c denote statistical significance at the 0.01, 0.05, and 0.10 levels, respectively.

Table 6: Tax avoidance, regional tax autonomy, size and group affiliation (matched sample using PSM)

Dep. var.	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
	ETR	ETR	ETR3Y	ETR3Y	ETR/STR	ETR/STR	ETR3Y/ STR3Y	ETR3Y/ STR3Y
ETR _{t-1}	0.167 ^a (0.030)	0.169 ^a (0.030)						
ETR3Y _{t-1}			0.235 ^b (0.119)	0.236 ^b (0.120)				
ETR/STR _{t-1}					0.168 ^a (0.027)	0.170 ^a (0.027)		
ETR3Y/STR3Y _{t-1}							0.228 ^a (0.074)	0.168 ^a (0.061)
BCD	-2.423 ^a (0.347)	-2.453 ^a (0.344)	-3.256 ^a (0.922)	-3.016 ^a (1.045)	-8.053 ^a (1.159)	-8.185 ^a (1.160)	-7.993 ^a (2.947)	-11.778 ^b (5.523)
NAD	-3.018 ^a (0.589)	-3.018 ^a (0.586)	-2.859 ^a (0.640)	-2.867 ^b (1.399)	-10.315 ^a (2.140)	-10.257 ^a (2.090)	-11.958 ^a (3.783)	-11.862 ^a (3.833)
SIZE	1.280 ^a (0.428)	1.077 ^b (0.441)	1.814 ^c (1.065)	2.843 ^b (1.119)	4.129 ^a (1.318)	4.007 ^b (1.814)	8.324 ^a (1.897)	7.657 ^a (2.432)
GD	4.439 ^a (1.531)	4.690 ^a (1.704)	1.903 ^a (0.694)	2.142 ^a (0.756)	7.495 ^b (3.818)	7.899 ^c (4.264)	4.786 ^b (1.930)	5.655 ^b (2.442)
SIZE×GD		-0.855 ^b (0.374)		-1.274 ^a (0.479)		-2.227 ^a (0.727)		-3.662 ^a (1.183)
OC	0.006 (0.021)	0.005 (0.022)	0.134 ^c (0.079)	0.020 (0.036)	0.028 (0.064)	0.023 (0.061)	0.121 (0.118)	0.105 (0.531)
ROA	0.057 ^c (0.029)	0.057 ^c (0.029)	0.019 (0.067)	0.021 (0.076)	0.203 ^b (0.094)	0.189 ^b (0.092)	0.032 (0.233)	0.281 (0.393)
AGE	-0.920 ^b (0.459)	-0.895 ^b (0.453)	-1.459 ^c (0.778)	-1.391 ^c (0.719)	-3.656 ^b (1.522)	-3.291 ^b (1.513)	-5.628 ^a (1.638)	-5.189 ^a (1.974)
PD	-0.766 (2.081)	-0.936 (2.129)	-2.131 (2.745)	-3.207 (4.521)	-1.857 (4.087)	-2.467 (6.434)	-9.937 (10.545)	-10.782 (11.719)
LOSS	-0.215 (0.238)	-0.283 (0.233)	-1.892 ^c (1.130)	-1.849 ^c (1.002)	-0.402 (1.088)	-0.747 (1.082)	-4.317 ^b (1.860)	-4.983 ^b (2.478)
IINT	-0.018 (0.064)	-0.024 (0.063)	-0.233 (0.244)	-0.260 (0.217)	-0.030 (0.227)	-0.055 (0.223)	-0.770 (0.880)	-0.638 (0.992)
CINT	-0.080 ^a (0.019)	-0.085 ^a (0.019)	-0.147 ^a (0.032)	-0.187 ^a (0.039)	-0.251 ^a (0.060)	-0.271 ^a (0.063)	-0.483 ^b (0.205)	-0.463 ^b (0.186)
SINT	-0.069 ^b (0.028)	-0.074 ^b (0.029)	-0.060 ^b (0.026)	-0.058 ^b (0.024)	-0.239 ^a (0.088)	-0.250 ^a (0.086)	-0.198 ^b (0.101)	-0.218 ^b (0.110)
LEV	-0.100 ^a (0.021)	-0.105 ^a (0.022)	-0.104 ^a (0.037)	-0.105 ^a (0.034)	-0.326 ^a (0.065)	-0.341 ^a (0.064)	-0.490 ^a (0.055)	-0.486 ^a (0.059)
RW	-0.259 (0.289)	-0.251 (0.290)	-0.827 ^c (0.432)	-0.791 ^c (0.406)	-0.740 (0.915)	-0.670 (0.916)	-1.698 ^b (0.727)	-1.865 ^b (0.829)
EXP	-0.280 (0.567)	-0.185 (0.546)	-0.686 (1.209)	-0.482 (1.103)	-1.392 (1.795)	-1.267 (1.781)	-1.161 (1.451)	-1.433 (1.635)
FSUB	0.036 (0.120)	0.036 (0.129)	-0.131 (0.178)	-0.202 (0.285)	0.185 (0.390)	0.194 (0.404)	-0.593 (0.525)	0.107 (0.543)
STR	0.523 ^a (0.119)	0.530 ^a (0.118)	0.903 ^c (0.461)	0.968 ^c (0.502)				
Intercept	7.661 (7.437)	1.967 (9.300)	2.653 (2.293)	2.593 (2.627)	7.585 ^b (3.301)	6.425 ^b (2.881)	2.252 (3.663)	3.347 (5.661)
Year F.E.	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Industry F.E.	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	11,288	11,288	11,084	11,084	11,288	11,288	11,084	11,084

Note: This table reports the coefficients and their corresponding robust standard errors (in parentheses) for eight panel data estimations. All columns show the estimates generated by the system GMM dynamic panel estimator using a two-step estimation procedure, with finite-sample correction applied to variance. The matched sample is composed of pairs of firms, one from tax autonomous regions and one from common territory, which have been identified by applying the Propensity Score Matching procedure. The sample in all cases encompasses both group-affiliated and stand-alone firms. In columns 1 and 2, the dependent variable represents the annual ETR, truncated between 0 and 100%. In columns 3 and 4, the dependent variable is the long-term 3-year ETR, similarly bounded. Columns 5 and 6 display the annual ETR relative to the STR, while columns 7 and 8 showcase the 3-year ETR relative to the average STR over the same period. All estimations account for year and industry fixed effects. All columns incorporate observations from firms that have provided data on all variables for a minimum of five consecutive years to assess the absence of second-order serial correlation. For a detailed description of the variables, please refer to Appendix B.

a, b, and c denote statistical significance at the 0.01, 0.05, and 0.10 levels, respectively.

Appendix A: Statutory corporate tax rate. Common territory vs. Foral territories

Region/year	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Basque Country	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	28
Navarre	32.5	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	25	28
Common territory	32.5	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	28	25

Note: This table presents the statutory corporate tax rates in both common and foral territories of Spain spanning the years 2007 to 2016.

Appendix B: Variable definitions

Variable	Symbol	Definition
Annual ETR	ETR	This rate is defined as the total income tax expense divided by the pre-tax book income.
3-year ETR	ETR3Y	This rate is defined as the sum of the total income tax expense of the current year (t) and the 2 preceding years (t-1 and t-2), divided by the cumulative pre-tax book income of those 3 years.
Effective/Statutory tax ratio (annual)	ETR/STR	This rate is defined as the annual ETR divided by the STR in effect for the region where the firm's registered office is located during that year.
Effective/Statutory tax ratio (3-year)	ETR3Y/STR3Y	This rate is defined as the 3-year ETR divided by the average STR in effect for the region where the firm's registered office is located during the same period.
Basque Country dummy	BCD	This dummy variable equals 1 when the firm's registered office is in the Basque Country and 0 otherwise. This region has corporate tax autonomy and may have tax rules that differ from those of the common territory and Navarre.
Navarre dummy	NAD	This dummy variable equals 1 when the firm's registered office is in Navarre and 0 otherwise. This region has corporate tax autonomy and may have its own tax rules that differ from those of the common territory and the Basque Country.
Size	SIZE	This variable is measured as the log of the total assets of a company.
Group dummy	GD	This dummy variable equals 1 when a firm belongs to a business group and 0 otherwise.
Special zones	SZ	This dummy variable equals 1 if the firm is located in the Canary Islands, Ceuta, or Melilla and 0 otherwise. These regions have special tax rules within the common territory.
Ownership concentration	OC	This variable is the main shareholder's percentage of direct ownership in a company.
ROA	ROA	This variable is the return on assets of a company.
Age	AGE	This variable is the age of a company based on when it was incorporated.
Public dummy	PD	This dummy variable equals 1 when a company is listed on the stock exchange and 0 otherwise.
Tax loss carryforward	LOSS	This dummy variable equals 1 when a firm has had a negative net income in at least one of the previous three years (t-1, t-2 or t-3), and zero otherwise.
Intangible asset intensity	IINT	This variable is the ratio of intangible assets to the total assets of a company.
Capital intensity	CINT	This variable is the ratio of fixed assets to the total assets of a company.
Inventory intensity	SINT	This variable is the ratio of inventory to the total assets of a company.
Leverage	LEV	This variable is the ratio of total liabilities to the total assets of a company.

Governing political party: right-wing or left-wing	RW	This variable is a proxy for the political orientation of the governing political party (right-wing or left-wing) in regions with tax autonomy (the Basque Country and Navarre) and the rest of Spain. It equals 0 when the governing political party is considered left-wing and 1 when the governing political party is considered right-wing.
Export activity	EXP	This dummy variable equals 1 when a firm has export activity in current year, and zero otherwise.
Number of group subsidiaries abroad	FSUB	This variable is the number of subsidiaries that the corporate group where a firm is affiliated to has abroad in current year.
Statutory tax rate	STR	This variable is the statutory tax rate in the territory in which the firm's registered office is located.

Note: This table reports the variables used in the paper and their definitions.

Appendix C: Sample selection

	Firm-year observations
Firm-years with accounting data between 2007 and 2016	2.341.320
Less: Observations of inactive firms	-68.289
Less: Observations with Total assets<3.000 euros	-11.427
Less: Observations with missing values in the required variables	-1.714.686
Less: Observations with anomalous values (negative Fixed assets, Intangible assets or Inventory)	-7.750
Less: Observations with pretax income <=0	-164.976
Less: Observations with ETR <0 or ETR>100	-41.795
Less: Observations of firms with no data for at least 5 consecutive years	-213.163
Total single firm-year observations	119.234

Notes

^[1] <https://www.oecd.org/tax/beps/>; https://taxation-customs.ec.europa.eu/anti-tax-avoidance-directive_en

^[2] See <https://elpais.com/espana/2021-08-07/el-debate-fiscal-en-torno-a-madrid-agita-el-tablero-politico.html>, and <https://www.elmundo.es/economia/macroeconomia/2023/04/27/644a850ee4d4d88c4c8b4601.html>

^[3] Corporate income tax law 27/2014. <https://www.boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-2014-12328>

^[4] ZEC stands for “Zona Especial Canaria” (Canary Islands Special Zone) which is a low tax zone created within the framework of the Canary Islands Economic and Tax Regime for the promotion of the economic and social development of the Islands and to diversify their production structure.

^[5] Consistent with existing empirical tax research, we use the term “tax avoidance” throughout the paper, but the term can be used interchangeably with the terms “tax aggressiveness” and “tax management” (Chen et al., 2010; Lanis and Richardson, 2012; Landry et al., 2013).

^[6] We address this issue in our robustness section.